

Graduation Thesis

Green schoolyards for enhanced socio-ecological resilience:

A multisystem perspective for
school and neighbourhood

Green schoolyards for enhanced socio-ecological resilience

Toka Ahmed

Student Number: 172259

Email: Toka.3798@outlook.com

Course: International Spatial Development

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Company Supervisor: Renet Korthals Altes

Lecturer Supervisor: Zhan Goosen

Research: Green Schoolyard

Company: Space for Play

University: Breda University of Applied Science

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AIS: Amsterdamse Impulse schoolpleinen	57
BMI: Body Mass Index	22
CLOCC: Consortium to Lower Obesity in Chicago Children	41
CPS: Chicago Public School	39
GSR: Green Space Ratio	34
LTL: Learning through Landscapes	17
NDVI: Normalized difference vegetation index	34
SBO: Spciaal Basisschool Onderwijs (Special elementary school Education)	59
SER: Socio-Ecological Resilience	25
USGBC: U.S. Green Building Council	15

PREFACE

This thesis, titled “Green schoolyards for enhanced socio-ecological resilience: A multisystem perspective for schools and neighbourhoods”, results from a final work as partial fulfilment for a Bachelor of Sciences degree in International Spatial Development at Breda University of Applied Sciences. At the beginning of the year, I never thought I could find an opportunity for my graduation thesis. However, likely, here I am doing an internship in two international organisations, “Sharnaqa” and “Space for play”, and finished my thesis in the most challenging time – corona time.

In truth, I could not have achieved my current level of satisfaction without a strong support group surrounding me during these four months. First of all, my supervisors, each of whom has provided patient advice and guidance through the research process. Renet Korthals Altes, my company supervisor, supported me with all the time and information, sharing knowledge about green schoolyards and playing for children, and all the pleasant memories and experiences in Egypt. I enjoyed working with you very much. Zhan Goosen, my university supervisor, supported me with her critical feedback and gave me the answers I am looking for with patience and professionalism. Secondly, my parents and sisters supported me with understanding and love from day one.

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Toka Ahmed
Breda University of applied sciences
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SUMMARY AND APPLICATION

This research paper aims to understand the impacts of greening schoolyard on the school and the surrounding neighbourhood based on the socio-ecological resilience model's multisystem approach. The first chapter forms the foundation of the greening schoolyards' definition, resilience, and socio-ecological model. It continues by addressing the role of the greened schoolyard to enhance (natural, built, social and health) resilience on the school scale through its impacts. The next chapter is structured the same as the previous chapter but on the neighbourhood scale. The fourth chapter consists of the empirical analysis to compare the outcome in three different cases identified from Europe and the U.S. Finally, the research will end with a conclusion and recommendations chapter.

The paper aims to broaden the conversation on the socio-ecological system by considering the potential for multifunctional green schoolyards to contribute to greater resilience in the face of an unpredictable future challenged by climate variability and availability and equitable distribution of resources.

It is hoped that these findings will further be used to study the benefits of green schoolyards in support of children's development and community resilience over the globe. With this research for Space for Play, it contributes to disseminating green schoolyards and resilience knowledge to international planners and other decision-makers on the green schoolyard by raising the knowledge that the development and construction of a schoolyard is a way to enhance school and neighbourhood resilience. This could support the development of green schoolyards internationally, in most of the cities where greening schoolyard didn't take place yet. Planners and decision makers can be encouraged to think and contribute to designing this green schoolyard in the layout of their environment.

Finally, this paper makes a case for a green schoolyard planning process at multiple scales, from the school to the neighbourhood. Such a multi-scalar approach could be used to identify and represent the interests of all stakeholders in the green infrastructure planning process, potentially leading to more equitable and sustainable outcomes. It is argued that this approach to planning could form civic environmentalism, promoting social cohesion and empowerment, health, and developing an environmental ethos among community members.

1 CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Chapter 1 provides the introduction and contextualisation of this research through elaborating on a problem statement, research questions, research objective, research methodology, and the research's structure.

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT MOTIVATING THIS RESEARCH

The public school districts are among the largest landowners in almost every city and town across the world (Danks, 2015). In the United States alone, over 98,000 public schools for primary education (Day, 2020). These schools manage a considerable amount of public land; in California, for example, it is 130,000 acres, making it some of the most well-used public land in the city. It is estimated that schools across the U.S. manage around 2 million acres in total (Day, 2020; U.S. Department of Education, 2015). Most elementary schools are filled with asphalt or concrete, although it is accessible to the community. This means it could negatively affect the school's children (Space to grow, 2019), and it impacts the disaster management process and significantly delays the evacuation and recovery process of the school and the surroundings (Valenzuela, 2017). Considering the number of disasters that affect cities, neighbourhoods, and buildings and the number of citizens, students, teachers, and communities involved have increased in the last years (Marana, 2018). These disasters are multisystem, demanding coordination of multiple adaptive systems to mount an adequate response. Integrating resilience across disciplines and scales is critical to meet the multisystem challenges of disasters (Masten et al., 2021).

Therefore, enhancing resilience by greening multiple schoolyards in cities has been a helpful concept and frame for strengthening and improving the system's function, particularly in urban development, disaster risk reduction, and climate action (Masten et al., 2021). The choices made by school districts on how they manage their landscape profoundly impacts the city and generations of residents whose perspectives are shaped through daily, outdoor experiences at school. Consequently, children, teachers and neighbours would benefit significantly from maximising the environmental opportunities of school grounds (Tranter et al., 2014). Besides the beneficial impact on the school scale, greening schoolyards could contribute to resilience in a multiple scaler approach (Masten et al., 2021). It starts from coping with extreme heat, flooding, and other increasingly disruptive climate-related events until it delivers benefits across multiple urban systems by empowering future generations to impact their surroundings and social integration (Flax et al., 2020).

This fact made city stakeholders more aware of the need to improve the way crises are managed by increasing greenery in public schoolyards. However, no one has quantified that land could have interdisciplinary impacts on different scales. The current researches focus only on a single disciplinary perspective; most of them are about health consequences of the children in school (Arntz, 2011; Chawla, 2014; Flax et al., 2020; Daniel, 2019; van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018; Dymont, 2005; Gordon, 2010; Grant, 2001). For this reason, the study will focus on the impact of greening schoolyards to enhance the **neighbourhood** and **school** resilience through influencing a multisystem urban approach. Multisystem resilience focuses on the notion of a 'coupled' social-ecological system that sees human society as dependent upon natural systems, and at the same time, the human agency acts as the driver of ecosystem dynamics (Figueiredo, 2021). Adopting this approach helps to clarify the importance and the power of greening the schoolyards by acknowledging the impact of greening on socio-ecological model aspects; which are the **Natural Environment** (green), **Built Environment** (grey), **Social Environment**, and **Health and wellbeing**; eventually, it leads to enhancement socio-ecological resilience in the neighbourhood and school.

1.2 RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVE

This research paper aims to understand and analyse the influence of greening elementary schoolyards interventions through a multisystem approach, referred to as the "socio-ecological resilience model" to reach resilient school and neighbourhood through:

- Understanding the resilience concept and SER (socio-ecological resilience) model;
- Understanding the impacts of greening schoolyard on environmental, social, built and health and wellbeing disciplines based on the SER model on school and neighbourhood;
- Realising practically the influences of the greening schoolyards based upon the SER model on the school and neighbourhood;
- Demonstrate the impact differences on the neighbourhood resilience between different greened schoolyards in different locations.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1.3.1 Main research question:

How can socio-ecological resilience model used to analyse the impacts of greening schoolyards in the school and neighbourhood?

1.3.2 Sub research questions:

What is the greening schoolyards concept in general?

What is the socio-ecological resilience model?

How could greening schoolyards enhance school resilience via SER model?

- What are the impacts on the natural environment at the school scale?
- What are the impacts on the built environment at the school scale?
- What are the impacts on the social environment at the school scale?
- What are the impacts on the health and wellbeing at the school scale?

How could greening schoolyards enhance neighbourhood resilience via SER model?

- What are the impacts on the natural environment at the neighbourhood scale?
- What are the impacts on the built environment at the neighbourhood scale?

- What are the impacts on the social environment at the neighbourhood scale?
- What are the impacts on the health and wellbeing at the neighbourhood scale?

How could the Socio-Ecological Model be used to frame “greening the school” Interventions? (Application)

Is opening the school to the public affecting the student and the community resilience?, How?

1.4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research will be based on qualitative data since this method is often more flexible and subjective. It is based on combining three frameworks, as shown in Figure 1. The first is the theoretical framework through literature study by analysing a segment of a published body of knowledge critically through summary, classification, and comparison of prior research studies, reviews of literature, and theoretical articles about greening the schoolyards, resilience. Using reference librarian and keywords related to school greening, physical activity, children and socioemotional health were used. The second framework is the analytical framework of the impacts based on the Socio-ecological resilience model that could be used to gain a deeper understanding of the impacts and the influences of this intervention. The third framework is the application framework is by looking for possible best practices in the United States and the Netherlands. They are the two leading countries in the greening schoolyard initiatives that implemented the green schoolyard concept (Loder, 2018) and analysing their impacts in three different situations. This framework is established through:

- Online desk research: by collecting data from existing resources about case studies
- Field visit: participant observation and visiting schools that executed this intervention, observing the student behaviour, and any natural and social changes.
- Interviews: it held with teachers to get a clear insight into greening influence in the school environment.

Figure 1: Framework methodology

1.5 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

This research has some notable limitations to point out. Firstly, the research is limited to the public elementary schools that have been greened their schoolyards, not including high schools or secondary schools. Secondly, it will not attempt to evaluate the impacts on the city scale through the multisystem approach and only mention it as a framework policy. The paper is focusing only on the primary school (with children as the main stakeholder) and the neighbourhood. Finally, it focuses merely on four factors from the socio-ecological model: natural, social, built, and health.

1.6 STRUCTURE OF THE RESEARCH AND CHAPTER DIVISION

This research was divided into six chapters. Following the preceding sections, the contents of Chapter 1 is evident. **Chapter 2: Greening schoolyards and resilience** introduces the literature with the green schoolyards concept, the definition and how they developed. In addition to that, the relation between the resilience in general and socio-ecological resilience model, particularly with greening schoolyards concept. **Chapter 3/4: Impacts of greening schoolyards to enhance school/neighbourhood resilience** forms the analytical section of the study, which discusses all the impacts of the socio-ecological resilience model's layers in school/neighbourhood to analyse their impacts and link it with school/neighbourhood resilience. **Chapter 5: Empirical investigation** aims to illustrate best practices and planning approaches utilising case study review, looking for best practices and the impacts of the green school in real life based on the same SER model. It aims to clarify the impacts of the greening schoolyards in three primary schools. Two in the Netherlands and one in the U.S. demonstrate the impacts of opening or closing the greened schoolyard from the public, does it affect the neighbourhood resilience. **Chapter 6: Conclusion** aims to conclude the report and suggest recommendation to encourage the city stakeholders to increase the initiatives of greening schoolyards and enhance the awareness of the relation between greening schoolyards to increase the overall city resilience.

2 CHAPTER 2: GREEN SCHOOLYARDS AND RESILIENCE

INTRODUCTION

Chapter 2, is the foundation chapter of the research paper that addresses the basic definitions, key terms and models through a literature review of the prior studies. The chapter starts with the definition of the green schoolyard, then the resilience in brief, then the socio-ecological model will be explained, and the relation between green schoolyards and the model.

2.1 GREEN SCHOOLYARDS

Greening schoolyard initiatives have been developed worldwide in the last two decades by various international and national programs, with numerous schools participating in this approach (Kerret et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2015). In 1997, the Learning through Landscapes organisation (LTL) had improved one-third of Britain's school grounds, and it has inspired a similar programme in Canada, "Learning Grounds" and a Swedish programme, "Skolans Uterum", and also in the USA, there are several organisations dedicated to improving their schools (Tranter et al., 2004) such as "Space to Grow" in Chicago. While in Amsterdam the program of greening schoolyards called "Amsterdamse Impulse Schoolplein".

Greening schoolyards is designed by adding vegetable gardens and trees in the playground or on-campus or hedges surrounding the premises (Hiemstra, 2017) and used in a way that invites and encourages each child to play, interact and learn in and with nature in ways that foster all aspects of their development and well-being (van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018). Green schoolyards are "school grounds where natural elements are present and abundant" (Stevenson et al., 2020); they may include playground equipment, sports facilities, community gathering spaces, accessible pathways, outdoor classrooms, storage, stormwater capture elements, nature play settings, trails (Jansson, 2014). Most critically, they include native vegetation (trees, shrubs, grassland, flowers, etc.), pollinator and edible fruit and vegetable gardens, associated animal life, and other natural features such as boulders, the unique biome surrounding the school (Stevenson et al., 2020). Bates et al. (2018) described greening schoolyards as an outdoor merged to nature "Green schoolyards are multi-purpose, environmentally beneficial spaces that incorporate natural elements, such as gardens, wooded areas, and green spaces, with traditional play features, and often include outdoor classrooms or learning components as well" (Bates et al., 2018). In line with Bates et al. (2018), van Dijk-Wesselius (2018) described the greening schoolyard as "an outdoor school environment where natural elements such as

trees, flowers, sand, water, grass, hills and bushes are combined to create a more appealing schoolyard and improve the quality of children’s experiences” (van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018). Therefore, the definition that this paper will rely on is “Green schoolyard” as School ground greening when greenery is added to existing school grounds merged by playing area and multi-purpose land use for children and the neighbourhood.

2.2 RESILIENCE

2.2.1 Resilience definition:

Although resilience has different definitions within the literature, it shows consistency in the description since it is described as the capacity to achieve good outcomes or bounce back from adverse factors (Maras, 2016; Study International, 2018). In a study done by Rojas (2015), resilience is defined as the processes of adapting in the face of adversity and the combination of **protective factors** and **risk factors**. Risk factors are the factors that increase the likelihood of a future negative result and outcome. Protective factors refer to those variables that buffer against the effects of risk factors (Masten et al., 2008; Rojas, 2015).

Definitions and models of resilience shifted to reflect the growing need to integrate knowledge about resilience across levels and disciplines to address multisystem threats and risks (Leng, 2020). In literature by Masten et al. (2021), resilience is defined for scalability and integrative purposes as the capacity of a dynamic system to adapt through multisystem processes to challenges that threaten system function, survival, or development. The alignment of resilience factors observed in human systems, ranging from individuals to communities, recommend the possibility of multisystem protective factors to work (Masten et al., 2021).

2.2.2 Socio-ecological resilience model:

The Socio-Ecological Resilience (SER) Model is a conceptual framework of urban resilience showing spheres of influences (Leng, 2020). Core principles of the layers in the SER model (Figure 2) are multiple influences as an individual, social, institutional, and policy influence (Leng, 2020). The interactions of those factors and the multilevel approaches can be applied to interventions intended to modify and add an impact (Lanza et al., 2021; Nassar, 2015). This model addresses population-level influences as well as individual-level impact (Theoretical Support behind Networks and Coalitions).

Figure 2: Socio-ecological Model (Leng, 2020)

2.3 GREEN SCHOOLYARD AS SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL SYSTEM

In the study by Masten et al. (2021), she claims adaptation of children in disasters depends on the resilience of interconnected systems, including schools, families, communities. Implications of a multisystem perspective for disaster risk preparedness and reduction, focusing on nurturing the resilience of children and their communities for challenges in the short and long term (Masten et al., 2021). According to Mell (2009), the green space must benefit the ecological and social actors and highlighted the potential for providing several multi-scale benefits (Mell, 2009). Local greening projects in schools can lead to social and ecological transformation at higher levels, with implications for the equitable distribution of resources, including ecosystem services (Lovell, 2013). Clearly stated that the greening schools have two levels of impacts (Gordon, 2010). First, globally, it contributes to the stewardship of resources and looks to the needs of future generations. The second is thinking locally, considers the health, safety, and welfare of people within the community, including students, administrators, and visitors (Gordon, 2010; Tranter et al., 2004). The various greening school projects show the obligatory attention to how the decision-makers are situated explicitly within multiple levels of the educational system. It includes the micro-level of daily preparation, the meso-level of institutional and systematic structures, and the macro-level social forces that shape the education systems (Dyment, 2005).

In that sense, it seemed that greening schoolyard is interlinked to both multi-scale such as school, communities and families, and multisystem approaches, such as environmental and social contexts and efforts to tackle the global aspects of the climate change problem. This 'coupling' of the social with local environmental and global climate constraints requires a new consideration of inter-linkages, and relations and how societies organise themselves (Lee et al., 2017), and the link between built environment of the schoolyard designs are closely connected with nature, children health (Magzamen, 2017; Younger, 2008) and society (Almanz, 2012; Tranter et al., 2004; Zhao et al., 2015).

Therefore, the SER model has been modified to fit four interrelated levels (spheres) in each scale then to combine the two levels into one model as in Figure 3. This framework guides how multilevel intervention can maximise the potential for socio-ecological resilience on both scales, school and neighbourhood (Lee et al., 2017) based on four main layers **Natural Environment**, **Built Environment**, **Social Environment** and **Health & wellbeing**. It assumes that multiple levels of impacts exist, and these levels are interactive and reinforcing (Golden et al., 2012).

To end up this chapter, Table 1 provides definitions for the primary key terms that form the basis of this paper:

Figure 3: Extending of Socio-ecological resilience model

Table 1: Main key terms definition

Greening Schoolyard	Greenery added to existing school grounds merged by playing area and multi-purpose land use for children and the neighbourhood (Bates et al., 2018; van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018).
Resilience	A dynamic system can successfully adapt to challenges that threaten the system's function, survival, or development (Masten et al, 2021) to promote protective factors: qualities in a person, the person's context, or interactions with the environment that predict better outcomes despite the risk (Chawla, 2014).
Social-ecological resilience	System that incorporate multiple levels of the organisation and systems to be more resilient in the face of small-scale change and disasters. Because change is inherent to all systems, resilience is an integral component of sustainability (Krasny, 2009)
Natural environment:	In the light of social responsibility is the natural surroundings in which human life occurs (Lauesen et al., 2013). It has a central role in advancing the understanding of human interactions with the natural environment and could prove pivotal in developing comprehensive theories and cope climate change (Ulrich, 2009).
Built environment:	The built environment includes building and infrastructure that constitute the natural, physical, and social capital that has also been adapted to address the relation between the built and the 'unbuilt' environment (Hasster, 2014).
Social environment:	It is an effective vehicle for promoting positive social development because of the opportunities to develop supportive relationships and experience personal growth by acquiring life skills (7 Physical and Social Environmental Factors, 2013).
Health and wellbeing:	It refers to the actual physical health of student/community, as defined by physical symptomatology and physical illnesses and diseases. The second is to the mental, psychological, or emotional aspects of student/community as indicated by emotional states and mental illnesses and diseases (Danna, 1999).

3 CHAPTER 3: GREEN SCHOOLYARDS FOR IMPROVED SCHOOL RESILIENCE

INTRODUCTION

The chapter's main objective is to discuss the impacts of greening schoolyards in a comprehensive approach and link their contribution to the school and the children's resilience. Hence, the following chapter clarifies how adding green to the schoolyard affects all the socio-ecological factors (environmental, urban, social, and health) separately. Then, it emphasises the importance of greening schoolyards initiative to school resilience as a building and student against global pressures and in a healthy environment.

3.1 NATURAL IMPACTS (SCHOOL SCALE)

The benefits of nature in general and in schools specifically are well documented (Danks, 2018). Green schoolyards contribute to improved environmental quality in physical improvements to the schoolyard, cultivating ecological stewardship's lifelong values (Plovnik, 2015) and reduced noise pollution (Loder, 2018). Green schoolyards features can moderate place-based climate change (Lanza et al., 2021); it can play an essential role in the microclimate of the school building (Mohamed, 2012) and promote habitats protection (Zhao et al., 2015). Schoolyard landscape planted with native vegetation can complement local habitat conservation plans and add many additional acres to support wildlife (Danks, 2018). This chapter section will focus on the software impacts on the children's mindset and attitude toward nature and hardware impacts to create climate resilience in the school.

3.1.1 Environmental stewardship and enhance environmental behaviour:

Green schoolyards can provide opportunities for children's learning, including botanical knowledge and positive attitudes to the environment and nature (Jansson, 2014). The increase in knowledge about environmental problems may raise children's concern and awareness (Zsóka, 2013). The impact of green in the schoolyards on young students can have a long-term positive effect. Students become better stewards of the environment (Danks, 2018). In a study explored how green space approaches influence children's school ground use and experiences through a series of field observations at a school in Malmö, Sweden. It stated that vegetation has a particular potential to involve children by providing opportunities to interact with the environment quickly and contribute to change. Children appreciate nature-like settings in proximity to school grounds for hands-on play opportunities. By providing various plants in a way that children can easily enjoy in school grounds and it can promote children's development of a positive and caring relationship with nature (Jansson, 2014). Contact with natural habitats at an early age not only allows children to develop a positive view or affinity towards nature but also it can make them local stewards in their adulthood (Baró et al., 2021) since the environmental stewardship and conservation behaviours are carried forward into adulthood (Danks, 2018).

Schoolyard greening is an effective way to promote interdisciplinary learning about the environment through projects that benefit the children (Grant, 2001). In a study done by Kerret et al. (2014) about anti-environmental behaviour, she reported that when students' social environment adheres to pro-environmental values and behaviours, it supports students' ability to overcome the difficulties of practising environmental behaviour and actually to engage in such behaviour. However, when anti-environmental behaviour is prevalent or in the face of pressure to act in anti-environmental ways like hurting animals, corrupting nature, consuming unnecessary products, or wasting resources such as water or electricity, then students' ability to exert resistance to peer pressure is an essential moderator for them to carry out environmental behaviour. Green schoolyard can reduce the negative peer pressure placed on students to act in anti-environmental ways by creating values, behavioural norms, and an overall school climate supporting environmental behaviour and criticising anti-environmental conduct. Although green schoolyards do not directly aim to impart self-control skills, it is reasonable to suggest that a reciprocal relationship exists between the learning of environmental behaviour and the teaching of self-control skills, especially because environmental behaviour is sometimes perceived as annoying, inconvenient, and requiring sacrifice. Hence, the report expects a reduction in students' anti-environmental behaviour in the green schoolyard (Kerret et al., 2014). Consequently, the students can appreciate school outdoor greenery such as street trees along their daily home-school routes, especially if they commute to school on foot (Baró et al., 2021).

3.1.2 Reduce heat stress:

Green schoolyards are increasingly recognised as shelters against climate change impacts (Baró et al., 2021) through creating a heat resilience area. Specially, in current times of the COVID-19 pandemic and more frequent heatwaves, natural outdoor spaces can indeed provide safer and cooler environments for children than traditional classrooms (Baró et al., 2021).

Dense trees create shading above playgrounds increase thermal comfort during warmer weather (Hiemstra, 2017). The converted schoolyards had more intense cooling effects than these normal asphalted schoolyards (Mackey, 2012). Lanza et al. (2021) studied the relation between green space and heat island in three joint-use elementary school parks in Central Texas, United States, it stated that greenspaces in schools lower air temperatures through shading and evapotranspiration from vegetation and improve human thermal comfort. Green schoolyards can serve as a tool for urban heat island adaptation via elements such as trees, gardens, and nature trails that inherently provide more opportunities for children to interact with nature physically (Lanza et al., 2021).

3.1.3 Managing water system:

The Centre of Green School USGBC had emphasised that the general impacts of the green schoolyards are removing toxic materials from places where children learn and play, reduce the burden on wastewater treatment and municipal water, conserve fresh drinking water and helps manage stormwater runoff (Zhao et al., 2015). Large amounts of impervious surfaces are able to manage stormwater (Plovnik, 2015), conserving rainwater and purifying urban runoff (Danks, 2018). For instance, certain design elements in the green schoolyard design can mitigate stormwater flooding and decreases pollutant loading of stormwater in heavy rain events if stormwater is captured on the schoolyard (Stevenson et al., 2020).

3.1.4 Improve air quality:

Air quality is often lacking in schools, or volatile organic compounds from construction materials may also be present. Green in schoolyards can help to improve air quality both indoors and outdoors, benefiting overall health in the long term (Hiemstra, 2017; Zhao et al., 2015). The vegetation limits the flow of air pollution from busy roads into school. Given enough light and water, helping to reduce ambient CO₂ levels, plants absorb CO₂ from the air (Hiemstra, 2017).

Link to School Resilience

Green schoolyard can support efforts to enhance climate resilience in the school building because it enables resource management to identify opportunities to reduce risk through physical and mental natural interventions (Houghton, 2010). The suggested risks such as heat stress, the risk of flooding, and air pollution. Green renovation in the schoolyard supports it mentally by enhancing the **students' environmental mindset, promoting students' behaviour** toward the environment, and **raising their awareness**. Besides, it creates long- and short-term climate-resilient schools by **preventing flooding** and **reducing air pollution** and **heat-related illness**. Green schoolyard practices nurture climate change resilience; therefore, green schoolyards are contributing to overall natural environment resilience in school scale.

3.2 BUILT IMPACTS (SCHOOL SCALE)

Nature could be integrated to the built components of urban systems (Back to SER model) by incorporating the design forms and features and natural processes through planning and design of the school (Rędzińska, 2020). On the school scale, some ecological factors influence the built environment and the design of the school, especially in the landscape vegetation. This including trees and gardens that is planted in each school to provide learning, visual enhancement, play and recreation opportunities, and a welcoming and calming environment (Lanza et al., 2021). Children's perceptions of the built environment may differ significantly from the others. Hence, it is important to understand children's opinions in their school context and build a place to meet their needs (Michail, 2021) and that what a green schoolyard could add to the children.

3.2.1 Great place:

The "Children & Nature Network" describes green schoolyards as **multi-functional** resilient school grounds designed for the school community, including places for parents, teachers, and students members to play, learn, explore and grow (Loder, 2018). The green schoolyard offer the **image** to the children by including water features, possibilities for children to choose their play activities and create their play places, and also **comfort** factors such as fields to play on; places and features to sit on, lean against or hide in; and an unstructured and manipulable environment (Baró et al., 2021). The green schoolyards provide **accessibility** by having access to nature such as trees, ponds, shrubs, flowers, long grass, insects, and animals (Tranter et al., 2004). All these keywords like functionality, accessibility, image and comfort, activities are linked to The Place Diagram in Figure 4. This Great Place diagram is an overarching and broad initiative surrounding the recreation and activation of spaces into inviting and vibrant areas to re-establish a sense of place and reconnect people with their environment (Peinhardt, 2021).

Figure 4: The place diagram (PPS, 2018)

3.2.1.1 Outdoor learning:

Children learn in schools but also from the school environment (Watchman, 2020). As natural outdoor spaces can indeed provide an innovative learning environments for children than traditional classrooms (Baró et al., 2021). Dymont (2015) investigated the outdoor learning environment as it is now strongly supported at a national level in the U.K. through the Learning through Landscapes organisation (LTL). In the U.K., the benefits of outdoor learning on a school ground are quite similar to the evident benefits of learning in other locations, such as field centres, camps, or zoos. Researchers who have investigated the potential of green schoolyards as outdoor classrooms, they found that when the context for learning changes from an indoor environment to a nature-centred environment, students find the schoolyard more meaningful area for education. Learning achievement is enhanced because green schoolyard provides

opportunities for learning about interconnections with nature. For instance, instead of seeing subjects as discreet entities, students experience first-hand the interconnections between issues (Dyment, 2005). Increased sensory stimulation is one of the benefits of naturalised spaces. Enveloped by colours and smells in areas replete with ever-changing textures makes children become unified with their surroundings (Danks, 2018; Moore, 2013). With an increasing number of elementary schools greening their schoolyards, opportunities arise to realise outdoor learning in natural areas on the school (van Dijk-Wesselius, 2020).

3.2.1.2 Variety of Play Areas and Activities:

Play becomes a necessary form of learning, and the quality of play is influenced by the opportunities provided in a child's environment, including their school (Tranter et al., 2004). Since the student perceives the functions of a landscape and uses it for play, the landscape might have a functional impact on play performance (Fjørtoft, 2001). The green surfaces are more suitable for particular types of free play than blacktop surfaces (Danks, 2018). Green schoolyard design could be a place where it accommodates a multitude of types of play. It offers a quiet, shaded area for gentle games. Other zones create a place for energetic and active play. This adds to green schoolyard renovations may impact several components of safety and comfort, including the schoolyard's overall condition, for example, risk of injury during play (Bates et al., 2018). When children feel stressed or tired, they may wish to have some privacy, and when they feel bored, they can move to areas with more exciting play opportunities. The children can easily find such places in the schoolyards (Tranter et al., 2004). The new greened schoolyard creates a variety of play environments in the school ground (Tranter et al., 2004) and offering various play type, according to Lamar (2016):

- Dramatic play: Loose parts—such as sticks—engage the imagination.
- Exploratory play: Green areas provide opportunities for children to explore in the school.
- Solitary play: Areas under bushes allow children to engage in alone time and contemplation.
- Locomotor play: Looping paths allow walking, running and biking in nature.
- Constructive play: Constructing and building things out of natural materials

Raney et al. (2019) collect data with direct observation and accelerometers pre-, immediately post-, and 4 months post-greening with 393 students enrolled. It showed that green space became the most popular space for experimental students who transitioned from traditional playgrounds for games and sports to chasing, gymnastics, climbing, jumping, and creative play (Raney et, 2019). The children's favourite places are often natural environments and associate them with calm and relaxed feelings (Dopko, 2019).

3.2.1.3 Sense of belonging:

Tranter et al. (2018) is geographical research to explore the impact of school grounds on children's play behaviours in primary schools to emphasise the importance of interaction between the children and their space in the green schoolyards to create a place to belong. It showed that an integral component of children's play in green schoolyards is the strong sense of place. The children, by interacting with their environment they become able to name specific space in the schoolyard. Naming places is essential because speech is a component of the total force that transforms nature into a place they belong to. The importance of children to be able to manipulate their environment has long been recognised as vital to children's play. There

are many advantages in allowing children to play with loose materials (branches, tires, wood, pinecones, stumps) to enhance children's environmental learning when building something, manipulating materials, and contributing to their sense of place. They get experienced when they have the freedom to explore their surroundings actively. In many schools, exciting parts of the school grounds are declared out of bounds for the children, thus reducing children's sense of place (Tranter et al., 2004).

Link to Student Resilience

As noted, the notion of the built environment can be considered an arena where a certain number of interactions and actors become visible (Hassler, 2014). "The Place Diagram" approach stated that the green schoolyard provides vibrant places aimed to **student** resilience (Peinhardt, 2021). Firstly, the green schoolyard incorporates ecological thinking about resilience into the social discourse to the children through **outdoor learning**, including landscape or patch ecology in the school. Secondly, greening schoolyards add a quality of public space to the children's schoolyards and it enhances **various kind of play**, to improve the resilience of the children, since playing has a significant role in developing and enhancing student resilience (Morrison, 2007). Moreover, it creates the **sense of belonging** to the school and the researches show that building resilience in young people helps them feel they belong to something bigger when teens feel that they do or contribute matters on a larger scale (What is resilience?, 2009). Based on that green schoolyard could be benefit and foster student resilience.

3.3 SOCIAL IMPACTS (SCHOOL SCALE)

According to Morrison (2007), students in today's schools face daily challenges of living in communities and school environments that may not provide adequate emotional and social support (Maras, 2007). The following line will discuss green schoolyards' role in promoting students' social resilience in schools and the overall social environment in the school.

3.3.1 Improved Social Capital and Cohesion:

The school ground is one of the few places where the children can interact with their peers in a natural, outdoor environment (Tranter et al., 2004). Various researchers claimed that socio-emotional well-being (Bikomeye et al., 2021; Hiemstra, 2017; Raney et al., 2019), developed social skills and intellectual processes (Kuo, 2021) are sensitive to exposure to nature. Nature is an integrating medium for children by age, gender, racial difference, learning styles, psychomotor skills, and personality traits (Moore, 2013). In addition to that, nature in school plays an essential role in fostering social interactions (Amoly, 2014; Bates et al., 2018) and promote a sense of community that is essential for social cohesion in the school and it has been shown to facilitate social networking and encourage social inclusion in children (Braubach et al., 2017). Further, green schoolyards provide social environments for children to play with their peers, establish supportive social groups and multicultural relationships, and strengthen their overall emotional and relational well-being (Baró et al., 2021).

3.3.2 Improve Social Behaviour:

Contact the children with green could influence children's behaviour (Fjørtoft, 2001), behavioural development (Amoly, 2014; Fleckenstein, 2006), and risk-taking skills (Danks, 2018). Schools that are the most likely to experience bullying and fighting tend to be schools where children have limited access to natural spaces in the school (Tranter et al., 2004). Children need contact with nature and the chance for the sense that nature offers. If children have little contact with nature, they may be more likely to have negative, even aggressive, feelings towards each other (Tranter et al., 2004). Another study of green space and stress between 10-year-old German children reported that children who have access within 500m of a green area had fewer parent-reported behaviour problems than children having access to a greater distance from green space (Erdem, 2015). Green schoolyard could reduce the surrounding community gang activity like bullying and teasing (Bates et al., 2018). The type of play facilitated by the green schoolyards can influence children's social hierarchy. In school grounds where sport and other types of active play are prevalent, children with the most significant physical strength or coordination tend to be dominant. However, in schools that encourage games involving a cognitive element, a different social order can emerge (Tranter et al., 2004). The green schoolyard is a school setting where children can learn to co-exist with others and become independent problem solvers as it conveys a powerful message about human values (Ndhlovu & Varea, 2016).

Link to Student Resilience

The ability of the student to **interact socially** with others has been suggested as a characteristic of a resilient child (Maras, 2007). Therefore, it is realised that green schoolyard can improve the students ability to socially interact through the activities and green in schoolyards, that are vital for **fostering social atmosphere, enhance social cohesion** for all students, and increase students' connection or bond to others by providing socially vibrant places. It leads to student's social resilience.

Secondly, schoolwide standards for social behaviour can also improve adjustment by providing a vehicle for **building positive behaviours** since a green schoolyard enhances **student adjustment** and **social skills**. Therefore it contributes to the individual student resilience (Peinhardt, 2021). By coping risks such as poor social skills, lack of friends, and poor relationship with the teacher.

In the end, the green schoolyard can promote student's social resilience by focusing on the social setting between the peer group, create social capital and improve schoolwide social behaviour.

3.4 HEALTH AND WELLBEING IMPACTS (SCHOOL SCALE)

The outdoor natural environment has provided multiple beneficial effects on children's well-being (Baró et al., 2021). The researches show strong positive associations between (access to, exposure to, or engagement with) green nature and child well-being, including effects related to mental (Chawla, 2014) and physical health (Amoly, 2014; Api, 2015; Baró et al., 2021; Bates et al., 2018; Bikomeye et al., 2021; Braubach et al., 2017; Jansson, 2014; Lanza et al., 2021; Puhakka, 2019; Triguero-Mas et al., 2015).

3.4.1 Enhanced Physical health:

3.4.1.1 Increase physical activity:

By providing attractive and accessible green schoolyards, encourages students to spend more time outdoors and facilitate physical activity (Chawla, 2014); physical activity typically refers to sporting and fitness activities; physical education; active play and informal activity (Michail, 2021). Which, by its way, has been shown to improve cardiovascular health, neurocognitive development, and general well-being to prevent obesity, cancer, and osteoporosis (Almanza, 2012). The "Nature-based Solutions to Climate Change Adaptation" book demonstrated that increased greenness was positively associated with moderate to vigorous physical activity. Another study in Sweden found a positive association between access to high-quality green space and higher physical activity levels. These activities in green schoolyards are more restorative and beneficial for health than physical activity in non-natural environments (Braubach et al., 2017). Since green grounds generally invite children to be active and to create change (Jansson, 2014). Adding green nature to asphalt-covered schoolyards helps expose children to nature and increases daily activity levels (Raney et al., 2019). Another research highlighted that large green outdoor in schools encourage physical activity among primary-school-aged children. Also, it helps girls especially to keep active through the years, and children who play in green spaces that offer a variety of playtime activities demonstrate better motor development (van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018). Therefore, Green schoolyards increase physical activity and associated health benefits such as decrease sedentary lifestyle and obesity (Danks, 2018; Stevenson et al., 2020).

Decrease sedentary lifestyle:

According to Bates et al. (2018) research, children engaged in higher physical activity levels on the schoolyard's green playground areas than the concrete or asphalt surface areas (Bates et al., 2018). Green elements in school grounds increase physically active children at low or moderate levels (Jansson, 2014). In a study done by Raney et al. in California and Los Angeles about the impact of green playgrounds on the sedentary level in children. The percentage of students observed as sedentary decreased by 10.0% in green playgrounds (Raney et al., 2019). Hence, providing green schoolyards in the school for activity, may reduce daily sedentary behaviour (Moore, 2013), which has been associated with positive developmental outcomes among children and counteracting it during breaks (Bates et al., 2018; van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018), and it contributes to overweight related diseases such as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, obstructive sleep, Asthma, Vitamin D Deficiency (McCurdy, 2010). Therefore the children are affected by their greened schoolyards that change the sedentary behaviour per day.

Decrease obesity and related diseases:

Proximity to green space also influences children's weight (McCurdy, 2010). A systematic review of 60 studies from Australia, the United States, Canada, New Zealand and Europe on the relationships between green schoolyards and obesity indicators proved that 68% of papers found that green space is associated with reduced obesity (Api, 2015; Bates et al., 2018; Braubach et al., 2017). A pilot study that used community gardening and education in nutrition in the United States found that 17% of overweight and obese children had improved their BMI (Body Mass Index) classification by the end of the seven-week-long programme (Braubach et al., 2017). Young children at schools with green schoolyards spend more time outside and show lower rates of obesity (van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018). Vegetable gardening among students at green schoolyards helps mitigate a sedentary lifestyle among children (van Dijk-Wesselius, 2018) since it can increase children's intake of fruit and vegetables and improve levels of green literacy (Hiemstra, 2017). Children who are sufficiently active and have access to green are less likely to develop chronic diseases like obesity and type 2 diabetes (Lanza et al., 2021). Several studies in The Netherlands, Australia and the United Kingdom demonstrated statistically significant associations between greenness and reduced chance of having type 2 diabetes mellitus (Braubach et al., 2017). Therefore, having access to green in school could lower the risk of obesity and the related diseases.

3.4.1.2 Therapeutic benefits and Reduce illnesses:

There is evidence of the therapeutic benefits of engaging people with autism with nature (Braubach et al., 2017) and reduce levels of illness (Chawla, 2014). Besides, the biodiversity in schoolyards have been associated with better children respiratory health (Baró et al., 2021). Braubach et al. (2017) suggest that children's immune systems benefit from direct exposure or contacts with certain factors in the green space (Bates et al., 2018). It has been shown that children with more exposure to specific bacteria or allergens in their first year are less likely to have recurrent wheeze and allergic sensitisation, and it has been demonstrated that increased biodiversity in the environment around is linked with reduced risk of allergy for children, the greater exposure to commensal microorganisms, especially in early life (Braubach et al., 2017). At the same time, water vapour increases the relative humidity in classrooms, which can reduce the percentage of students suffering from headaches (Hiemstra, 2017). Hence, the biodiversity in greened schoolyards benefits the student's health and reduce the risk of various allergies and diseases.

3.4.2 Improved Mental Health and Cognitive Function:

There is evidence for a causal relation between urban green and mental health in children (Bates et al., 2018; Bikomeye et al., 2021; Braubach et al., 2017; Waters, 2010), such as child behavioural, cognitive development (Bikomeye et al., 2021) and academic achievement (Baró et al., 2021; Braubach et al., 2017), fewer discipline problems and increased student self-confidence (Plovnik, 2015). Renovated green schoolyards may encourage behaviours like lower levels of stress, anger, and problem behaviours (Bates et al., 2018).

3.4.2.1 Improve academic achievement:

Two observational studies linked greenness to academic achievement on several levels (Stevenson et al., 2020; Plovnik, 2015). As more greenness at school is associated with improved cognitive development, such as reduced inattentiveness in school children and better working memory progress (Braubach et al., 2017). Research has shown that greening schoolyards help students concentrate and raise attention levels (Hiemstra, 2017). Moreover, views on the green from classrooms where students take breaks helps restore concentration more quickly (Amoly, 2014). Other research shows that trees and shrubs outside classroom windows have been positively associated with high test scores, grades, and ambitions (Jansson, 2014). Outdoor learning on green school grounds helps to motivate and inspire students who do not learn best in the classroom (Dyment, 2005).

3.4.2.2 Reduce Stress and hyperactivity:

A quantitative study that surveyed 172 urban children from Spain found that children who are having greater access to nature in green schoolyards reported positive impacts on children's physiological stress (Kelz, 2015). Other research showed that lower levels of perceived stress than children with more insufficient access to nature (Amoly, 2014). Additionally, exposure to green nature buffered the association between reported adversity and perceived stress (Chawla, 2014), promoted positive coping (Bates et al., 2018), and it helps children recover from stress more quickly than similar spaces with little or no nature (Stevenson et al., 2020). Moreover, preschool children with access to large integrated areas of trees, shrubbery, and hilly terrain for play, have lower measures of forgetfulness, difficulty in listening, hyperactivity, and impulsivity, versus areas with less integrated vegetation (Chawla, 2014).

Link to Student Resilience

Physical resilience refers to the body's ability to exert its true power then return to a healthy resting state following exertion (forlines, 2019). Therefore the children need tools to enable them to take on challenges and maintain stamina and strength for their body job demands (forlines, 2019). It becomes evident that greening schoolyards maintain the children's physical stamina and strength; it decreases **obesity** and **type 2 diabetes**, improves **moderate to vigorous physical activity**, and **decreases sedentary**. Consequently, greening schoolyards contribute to improving students' physical health resilience at the school.

In the other hand, mental health competencies that promote resilience -including **stress management, sense of control, cognitive competencies, problem-solving**, and **intellectual ability** (Laura, 2013). As discussed above, all these competencies are achieved by greening schoolyard initiatives to enhance the students' mental health resilience since it brings relaxation response-based coping skills and life management tools into the school environment to help students better manage daily stress and positively impact students' academic performance and health (Benson, n.d.).

3.5 CONCLUSION OF THE SCHOOL SCALE

To sum up, the green schoolyard is an added green merged by the new design of the schoolyard, which means that it is a combination of the natural factor and the built factor from the SER model. Greening schoolyards have been proven to be one of the strategies to build and create school and student resilience via different systems; **Natural, Built, Social and Health** to provide a positive environment and healthy students based upon the socio-ecological resilience model.

Firstly, a green schoolyard contributes to school resilience. As stated previously, greening schoolyards deliver benefits across multiple urban systems, empowering future generations to impact their surroundings, social integration, water management, air quality, and providing new activities and uses. These schoolyards have the potential to reduce the stress of climate change and create place innovative public space for children.

Secondly, greened schools play a dual role in child resilience. They provide a host of resources, relationships that directly support child resilience and enhance protective factors for resilience in children. It offers compelling physical and mental health advantages for interventions because children are already connected to schools. Then, consequently, green schoolyards could enhance the resilience of children.

Finally, as shown in Figure 5, in some cases, it is only the addition of nature, regardless of the schoolyard design, which impacts resilience at the school level. Examples are enhancing the immune system through direct contact with nature in the health sector, while in the natural environment sector was reducing heat stress and improving air quality. Apart from this, built environment (schoolyard design) can impact the students physical and mental health without the combination with nature, like the playground added to increase the physical activity or create places to relax at the school in the health sector. But in general, the combination between the natural environment and the built environment impacts all the four layers in the SER model.

Figure 5: SER model for child resilience

4 CHAPTER 4: GREEN SCHOOLYARDS FOR IMPROVED NEIGHBOURHOOD RESILIENCE

INTRODUCTION

The socio-ecological resilience to have an impact must be created in local communities, neighbourhoods, and households (Lippman, 2013). The school is the same as a community hub since the local schools can greatly enrich community life (Annerstedt, 2012). Therefore, the green schoolyard can be designed with the community's unique needs and characteristics allows the neighbourhood to thrive. Hence, this chapter investigates the expected impacts of green schoolyards. The chapter's aim to address the impacts of a resilient green schoolyard on the neighbourhood based on the same four SER model approach: **Natural environment**, **Built Environment**, **Social Environment** and the **health and well-being** of the community by linking it eventually to the neighbourhood resilience as in Figure 6.

Community Resilience in the Neighbourhood

Figure 6: Green schoolyards socio-ecological model for community resilience

4.1 NATURAL IMPACTS (NEIGHBOURHOOD SCALE)

Access to green spaces in the neighbourhood was defined as the presence or not of green spaces within the 300m circular buffer, which includes green spaces or green urban areas such as agricultural land and pastures and non-urban green places like country parks or forests (Triguero-Mas et al., 2015). This means that green schoolyards could contribute to neighbourhood green space. Another study determined the residential greenness as an average of the satellite-derived normalised difference vegetation index in a 300m buffer around each house, and the proximity to green space was defined as the distance from the residence to the nearest green space (Birute, 2014). The following lines examine the importance of greening schoolyards for the neighbourhood resilience (in 300m) in overcoming the heat island effect, enhancing the ecological resources and stormwater management.

4.1.1 Reduce heat stress:

Research has reported that 35% of urban areas in the Netherlands experience heat stress at least seven days per year (Hiemstra, 2017), which negatively affects the general health well being (Shahmohamadi, 2011). This effect increases as built-up areas become denser, and extreme values or extended duration can also adversely affect health (Hiemstra, 2017). However, greenery can help to lower temperatures in a buffer zone of 300m (Mell, 2009). In the neighbourhood, greening schools moderates the climate in the summer. Research done by Schulman (2008) used GIS analysis on urban schoolyard landcover in three U.S. cities, suggests vegetation is essential for environmental health. Collectively termed urban vegetation, particularly trees, can mitigate the urban heat island, reduce urban runoff and nonpoint source pollution, and sequester air pollutants (Schulman, 2008). More specifically, schools are almost situated in urban areas, where the higher percentage of built-up and surfaced areas generally produces higher temperatures (the 'heat-island effect') so by greening multiple schoolyards could reduce the urban heat island in a neighbourhood (Hiemstra, 2017).

4.1.2 Ecological resources:

In a study done by Mell (2019), he stated that green schoolyards play a vital role in linking global water, energy, and carbon cycles controlled by environmental factors and vegetation dynamics in the neighbourhood. Creating green spaces allows ecological resources to be maintained that provide ecological sinks to mitigate environmental change. Green schoolyard can contribute by developing larger expanses of flora and fauna, water or green spaces, and developing ecologically critical infrastructure pockets within urbanised neighbourhoods. Thus, trees, gardens, play areas and parks all potentially hold substantial ecological value. If the green schoolyard is discussed in terms of the broader green matrix of urban and urban-fringe landscapes in the neighbourhood, it can provide a level of compensation for some of the effects of climatic change (Mell, 2009). In addition, green schoolyards could teach how the society can produce energy sustainably, mitigate climate change, become more locally self-sufficient, and protect the species and dynamic ecosystems (Houghton, 2010).

4.1.2 Stormwater management

Green schoolyard can act as ecosystem manager and natural resource sink or as a buffer to climate change by increasing the proportion of ecological resource and providing spaces that can adapt or control extreme variations in climate such as flooding in a neighbourhood. This can be achieved by providing green schoolyards where excess rainwater can be stored and dispersed (Mell, 2009). In research about the Blue-Green Infrastructure, stated that green landscape systems collectively provide multiple ecosystem services, including flood risk mitigation, water quality treatment, driven by the urgency to tackle different local challenges, such as water security, increased flood risk, water quality standards and aquatic ecosystem degradation (Liao, 2017). Then greenery added to the neighbourhood through the green schoolyard initiatives could help the neighbourhood to tackle stormwater challenges and reduce flooding.

Link to Neighbourhood Resilience

There is a broad consensus that neighbourhoods must become resilient to a more comprehensive range of stresses and become better prepared to tackle climate change and efforts to foster climate change resilience (Filho, 2020). Green schoolyard can contribute to ecological and natural resilience by improving the capacity of the neighbourhood ecosystem to respond to disturbance by resisting the damage and recovering fast such as **decreasing the heat island effect**. Besides that, the greened schoolyard **enriched the biodiversity and the ecological resources** in the community to tackle the risk of climate change-related problems, such as **flooding**. Hence, greened schoolyards are an opportunity for comprehensive climate adaptation and improve neighbourhood natural resilience.

4.2 BUILT IMPACTS (NEIGHBOURHOOD SCALE)

Creating resilient neighbourhoods should be the result of adequately implemented urban planning and design. For this to happen, school designs should contribute to the planning design of the neighbourhood because they shape the natural performance of planned areas (Rędzińska, 2020). According to Mell (2019), green space could promote and emphasise the following principles outlined in the green infrastructure research: connectivity, accessibility, multi-functionality (Mell, 2009). While Steveson (2020), green space would provide every community safe, accessible and natural (Stevenson et al., 2020). Compared to Ndhlovu (2016), greening space must address three fundamental components: access, activity and variability (Ndhlovu & Varea, 2016). It becomes clear that accessibility, connectivity, and activities are the main features in order to achieve a functional and well planned public green space for the neighbourhood. This chapter focuses on equal accessibility to the greenery spaces and how the schoolyard creates a public realm in the neighbourhood.

4.2.1 Green access equality:

In the rapidly urbanising planet, making cities safe, inclusive, resilient, and sustainable is one U.N. Sustainable Development Goal 11 includes “providing universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible green and public spaces, in particular for children and women, older persons and people with disabilities” (Baró et al., 2021). These are accepted by many as fundamental human rights, and research supporting how access to green schoolyards may be one of the strongest arguments for how green schoolyards can contribute to an equitable and just society resilience, in case it is open to public outside the school hours and in summer, when school is out, and kids and families have more free time to spend outside (Stevenson et al., 2020). Access to nature is an environmental justice issue for low-income or low levels of education who have less access to vegetation (Dyment, 2008; Stevenson et al., 2020). However, green space is not equally accessible or available to all residents in low-income communities. Often these communities are having a less green area or being exposed to vandalised, poorly maintained, or unsafe green areas (Braubach et al., 2017). Integrating nature into school grounds would ensure that every child in the neighbourhood has access to nature in places where they must spend a significant portion of their daily lives (Stevenson et al., 2020). Green schoolyards could become valuable local parks during out of school hours by allowing all communities to have access to schools. Focusing on greening schoolyards is one promising strategy for mitigating the barriers to access to nature (Stevenson et al., 2020). Cities such as Houston, New York, Denver, San Francisco and Boston have long been leaders in transforming schoolyards into high-quality green space (Davis, 2015). School greening initiatives prioritise those neighbourhoods with little exposure to natural environments (both within and around school settings) and consider aspects related to the socioeconomic status of school children (Baró et al., 2021).

4.2.2 Adding public space:

Green schoolyard has placed a greater value on landscape multi-functionality and the use of green infrastructure as a way of connecting people with the environment by developing better access to green spaces across urban areas (Mell, 2009). It is more likely to be if the schoolyard is designed as a shared space for the community and is open to the public during non-school hours (Stevenson et al., 2020). Thus, during out of school time, these schoolyards are ideally available for community use (Loder, 2018). Since the playgrounds are spaces designed to facilitate play and the interaction of children, but may also be places of interaction between parents (Bennet, 2012). A long-term solution to reducing community access to nature in the neighbourhood would involve making streets and neighbourhoods safer for children and allowing children to use more of their area as play space (Tranter et al., 2004). Moreover, in the neighbourhood with greater access to nature have lower theft and violent crime rates. This study were conducted in communities where social cohesion and violence were present, ensuring the potential for green schoolyards to contribute to safe and healthy communities (Stevenson et al., 2020) which means that green schoolyards can increase the social safety in the area.

Link to Neighbourhood Resilience

On the same principle as in the school scale (chapter 3), greening schoolyards act as a **public realm** (only if it is open to public) in the neighbourhood the same as the school. As a consequence, it contributes to the neighbourhood resilience and enhance it's vibrancy. It offers different activities for the residents and improves the **safety of the area**. In addition to that, it provides **fair access** to all the neighbourhood residents to green infrastructure (the SDG 11 from the U.N.). Therefore, it ends with more families and children playing outdoors, more communities with food gardens and more youth with green exposed. Moreover, it's suggesting that schoolyard greening is a viable intervention in reducing the equity gaps and ensuring the opportunity to all children in the neighbourhood to enhance their resilience regardless of their racial or ethnic backgrounds or residential neighbourhood socioeconomic status.

4.3 SOCIAL IMPACTS (NEIGHBOURHOOD SCALE)

Research indicates that feeling unsafe in a neighbourhood and the fear of being a victim of crime can decrease social cohesion and social ties among neighbours (Bateman, 2017). Thus, urban green spaces -in this paper are “green schoolyard” - may support and potentially influence the social fabric of urban areas in various ways in case it is open to public (Erdem, 2015). The social environment benefits from increasing exposure to quantity and the quality of greenery, include increased community cohesion and positively associated with a sense of community (Erdem, 2015; Stevenson et al., 2020; Ruijsbroek, 2017) and improve social well-being (Braubach et al., 2017) and community satisfaction (Van Herzele, 2012). In the following lines, the role of social cohesion and the social atmosphere in neighbourhood resilience will be discussed.

4.3.1 Social cohesion:

The development of social ties is affected by the characteristics of the neighbourhood green space (Kaźmierczak, 2013). At the same time, a shortage of green space has been associated with the perception of loneliness and lack of social support (Braubach et al., 2017). Improved social capital from parks and trails, contact with nature and locally grown food (Younger, 2008). Kaźmierczak (2013) suggests that local parks support the development of social ties in the neighbourhood. Associations were found between the gardens’ quality, the character of visits, and the extent of the social relations in the community. The study concludes that local parks can realise their full potential in supporting social interactions and developing social ties (Kaźmierczak, 2013). Another experimental research by Goldy (2020) supported the idea that exposure to nature can enhance social connection and solidarity. Specific pro-social behaviours linked to exposure to nature include better orientation to others and increased sensitivity to the needs of others. The research also shows that urban green space is associated with increased perceptions of social cohesiveness in one’s neighbourhood and volunteering. The feeling of being connected to nature is linked to enhanced perspective-taking. Furthermore, even exposure to images of nature can influence people’s willingness to help others (Goldy, 2020). Social interactions increased on renovated green schoolyards in urban, low-income neighbourhoods (Bates et al., 2018). These studies showed that green schoolyard can provide opportunities to know neighbours, build community ties in the neighbourhood, and increase social interaction and cohesion.

4.3.2 Social satisfaction:

Neighbourhood’s satisfaction with their neighbourhood differed significantly. The analysis study in Ghent, Belgium indicated that neighbourhood satisfaction fully mediates the relationship between neighbourhood greenness and happiness. Another study showed that the view from the living room green or not green fully mediates the relationship between neighbourhood greenness and neighbourhood satisfaction (Van Herzele, 2012). An evaluation is done by Space to grow in Chicago about the neighbourhood’s perceptions on greening the schoolyards. The evaluation results suggest that school transformation of green schoolyards improves perceptions of neighbourhoods among individuals living in the urban, low-income communities. Those who live in the greener neighbourhood were more satisfied than those who live in a less

green neighbourhood. Green schoolyards positively impacted the neighbourhood's perceptions since the caregivers reported being more attracted to living in the neighbourhood and feeling a greater desire to remain residents (Space to grow, 2019).

Link to Community Resilience

Social cohesion is the extent to which groups can help each other and is a fairly obvious way of building social resilience (Flax et al., 2020). Based on that, social resilience could be enhanced by adding green schoolyards to the community, as it improves the **social tie** between the neighbours, and **create social atmosphere**, and **increase the social safety** perception in the neighbourhood. Build a solid social resilience is one aspect improving the capacity of the communities to deal with external stresses and shocks (Erdem, 2015). This social resilience could contribute to community preparedness, disaster response, and post-disaster recovery. Hence, implementation of green schoolyards aims to build community resilience to minimise disaster vulnerability and promote effective collective responses in the neighbourhood.

4.4 HEALTH AND WELLBEING IMPACT (NEIGHBOURHOOD SCALE)

Resilience is related to improved physical and mental health, as many resilience studies have found evidence that it is possible to develop or maintain resilience to improve poor physical health. This implies that resilience can be used to improve well-being within an ill community (McGowan, 2018). Establishing a green schoolyard will increase the contribution of the green infrastructure in the neighbourhood; therefore, it enhances the benefits to support more extensive public health and municipal initiatives in the drive for more significant health equity (Loder, 2018).

4.4.1 Healthy and Active Lifestyle:

Greenspace makes outdoor activity enjoyable and easy and encourages less sedentary lifestyles (Braubach et al., 2017). Various studies in multiple countries have demonstrated that increased physical activity and reduced sedentary time were associated with access to green space in working-age adults, children, and senior citizens. Thus, in this case, green schoolyards are embedded within the green infrastructure might increase physical activity. Providing safe green schoolyard settings in urban areas resulted in increased physical activity and decreased sedentary behaviour among youth in that low-income neighbourhood (Bates et al., 2018). It will reduce cardiovascular mortality (Leng, 2020), obesity and, reduce mortality and increase the life span (Braubach et al., 2017). All these outcomes will be evident in the following lines.

4.4.1.1 Reduced Mortality and Increased Life Span:

The availability of green space is linked with a reduction in mortality. A study in Japan has reported that the five-year survival rate in the elderly was positively related to having access to green areas suitable for taking a stroll and parks near their houses. Another study in England showed that the pre-retirement age population that a greater area of green areas in the neighbourhood was associated with reduced all-cause mortality (Leng, 2020). A study in Canada found that increased residential green area was associated with reduced mortality; the most potent effect was on mortality from respiratory diseases. Research in the United States illustrated that the residential proximity to the green area had been associated with a decreasing risk of mortality and higher survival rates after ischemic stroke (Braubach et al., 2017). Therefore, increasing the greened area in the neighbourhood by greening schoolyards could reduce the mortality rate and increase the community's residents' life span.

Increased access to green space was linked to a reduced detrimental impact of income deprivation on cardiovascular mortality, as a study has provided evidence that the risk of cardiovascular mortality is lower in areas with higher residential greenness (Braubach et al., 2017). Research done by Leng (2020) showed that neighbourhoods residents had a higher risk of physical inactivity with a Green Space Ratio (GSR) lower than 28% suffer from hypertension and stroke (Leng, 2020). While in the study by Richardson (2013) showed that cardiovascular disease risk was reduced in all neighbourhoods with >15% green space availability (Richardson, 2013). Overall, green schoolyards contributed towards green infrastructure in the neighbourhoods, which lead to lower levels of cardiovascular mortality.

4.4.1.2 Healthy lifestyle:

A study in Germany demonstrated an inverse relation between greenness in the neighbourhood (measured by NDVI) and insulin resistance in adolescents (Braubach et al., 2017) which one of the obese-related diseases. Additionally, researches conducted by Nielsen (2017) and by Leng (2020) showed that using green space for gardening may influence physical activity and encourage healthy eating food, thereby reducing obesity (Leng, 2020; Nielsen, 2007). Moreover, keeping a vegetable garden can also filter it up to the parents from the students in the greened school (Hiemstra, 2017). Stems from that green schoolyards could improve the community's lifestyle since the yards include native gardens, vegetable gardens, trails, trees, water features, etc. (Children & Nature Network, n.d.).

4.4.2 Mental health:

The greener neighbourhoods had the lowest risks of poor mental health (Braubach et al., 2017), and it has been strongly associated with improved mental health. Most studies relied on measures of green availability as a proxy measure of exposure. At the same time, a study in Europe linked the time spent in green spaces with improved self-reported health and vitality. It has also been realised that the human microbiome associated with the natural environment may improve mental health (Braubach et al., 2017). Psychological relaxation has shown that individuals who live in residential areas with more green space tend to decrease the level of stress and better well-being (Nielsen, 2007) compared to those with insufficient availability of green space. More green spaces in the neighbourhood were linked to lower levels of depression, anxiety, and stress linked to enhanced mental well-being. A prospective study showed that moving to greener residential areas has been linked with mental health improvements (Kabisch, 2017). The statistical research indicates that access to a park or short distances to green areas from the house is less stressful (Nielsen, 2007). Several studies provided evidence that green spaces are especially beneficial for specific subpopulations or disadvantaged groups. For instance, a representative sample of the disadvantaged group showed that relocate to a neighbourhood with more access to green space has been associated with improved mental health (Kabisch, 2017). It becomes clear that greening multiple schoolyards in the neighbourhood and opening them to the public improve the mental health of the residents who live close by or who spend time in the schoolyard.

Link to Community Resilience

Community health resilience refers to the communities positive adaptation to the experience of adversity since it maintains mental and physical health is considered a sign of successful coping with adverse conditions (Färber, 2018). Green schoolyards increase the amount of green infrastructure in the neighbourhood therefore it helps to increase the physical health resilience toward risks of different diseases by **increasing the physical activity** and **healthy lifestyle** among the neighbourhood residents and it enhances the mental health of the neighbourhood from **stress** and **anxiety**. Consequently, it creates healthier communities who are more resilient communities.

4.5 CONCLUSION OF THE NEIGHBOURHOOD SCALE

Resilience schools play a central role in developing children and communities; therefore, the schools symbolise the community members' everyday lives and children and their parents. The benefits of green schoolyards extend to who are in schools; after a while, benefits extend to residents of the surrounding neighbourhood, especially children and youth. Green schoolyard makes neighbourhoods more socio-ecological resilient to disasters and various risk factors. Such as helping to tackle challenges that arise from urban flooding or heat island effects by increasing natural land cover and mimicking biological processes to manage stormwater. Besides, it creates a social environment in the neighbourhood and enhances the social ties with the neighbours. While in the built environment, the renovated schoolyards helped green access equity and created a public realm in the neighbourhood. Finally, it promoted communities physical and mental health resilience toward the risk of different illnesses.

The impact of the greened schoolyard in the neighbourhood requires different conditions in order to have a valid impact. Some of the impacts require the green schoolyards to be able to upscale or to be replicated in the neighbourhood. The other impact requires the schoolyards to remain open to the public outside of school hours, while the third condition is the access in the proximity area of buffer zone around 300m on the neighbourhood. To conclude, green schoolyards serve as a natural resource for the neighbourhood and create great communities since it is a multi-beneficial method to promote community engagement and social cohesion, improve health outcomes, and mitigate and adapt to climate change.

5 CHAPTER 5: EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

INTRODUCTION

This chapter will aim to illustrate best practices and planning approaches utilising a case study review. Three case studies will be analysed; the first school-based in Chicago, USA. The school called Morrill Elementary is located in the Chicago Lawn neighbourhood in southwest Chicago. The other two schools are in the Netherlands; one is located in Rotterdam called Hildegardisschool in Oude Noorden neighbourhood, and the other is Universum in Amsterdam Noord. These three schools are elementary schools constructed between 2011 to 2018. The first two case studies, “Morrill school” and “Hildegardisschool”, was analysed through desk research focusing on elements of natural, built, social and health impacts. The third case study of Het Universum green schoolyard was analysed by observing children’s play behaviour in the schoolyard during break time and interviews multiple stakeholders about the same four factors (natural, built, social and health). The interviews have been done with Jurre Noppers, he is a concierge at SBO Universum, and “Mona Fathallah”, mother of a fourth-year student in the school who was in the school before and after the greening and she lives in a proximate area from the school (for an interview setting see Appendix 1).

Participating schools were selected based on various criteria. The main selection criterion was that greening schools’ initiative is government subsidised and is a part of the municipal approach. The second criteria are the urbanisation of the neighbourhood where the school is located. Thirdly the neighbourhoods and the school should host by multicultural schools and communities.

The chapter investigates the impact of the greening the schoolyard, whether it is publicly accessible or not, on the neighbourhood and the school resilience. The first case study is Chicago’s green schoolyard which is open to the public, the Hildegardisschool’s schoolyard is semi-public, while the Universum is a non-public schoolyard. The findings of these three schools will be compared to investigate whether opening the greened schoolyard to the public affects the natural, social, built, and health resilience in the neighbourhood and the school or not.

CASE 1:

CHICAGO CITY, USA

DONALD L. MORRILL MATH & SCIENCE
SCHOOL

Student No.
300-400

Organization
Space To Grow

Location
Chicago Lawn Neighbourhood

Construction Year
2014

CITY CHALLENGES

Neighbourhood Flooding and Stormwater Management Challenges:

City of Chicago and its shore along Lake Michigan and rivers run through its neighbourhood face challenges with stormwater management and water quality (Shaped by Chicago, sd). Flooding and combined sewer overflows are significant problems in Chicago due to extensive rain events that its current infrastructure cannot handle (Davis, 2015). These challenges are associated with the effects of climate change, with more intense storms that can deposit vast amounts of rain in hours (Shaped by Chicago, sd).

Limited access to green and Outdoor Play areas:

Most Chicago residents lack access to green areas. 10% of Chicago's population does not live within a half-mile of a park, and this is the nationally recommended distance for healthy access to green space. Chicago has only nine playgrounds per 10,000 residents in the city, less than half of the recommended number of gardens for a population of that size. The heightened crime can sometimes limit access to little park space available. The lowest quarter for median household income is the most affected population by this limitation (Shaped by Chicago, sd).

GREEN SCHOOLYARD'S ROLE IN RESILIENT CHICAGO:

Chicago Public Schools (CPS) is the second-largest landowner in the city of Chicago. The district has 400,000 students housed in 681 buildings, and each school has at least 30,000 square feet of space available to build a schoolyard. Since forty percent of Chicago is covered with impermeable pavement, it is estimated that Chicago public schoolyards represent 763 acres of impermeable blacktop. Transforming these impervious surfaces on CPS properties means these schoolyards can become part of an integrated stormwater management solution (Davis, 2015). A report published by the city of Chicago about the resilience of Chicago city linked greening schoolyards approach to the city resilience (Resilient Chicago). The government prioritises schools with high flood risk and a lack of resident access to green or play space. Construction has been completed in planning at 19 CPS schools by 2018 (See Figure 7).

The program aims to capture stormwater and relieve local sewers by at least 150,000 gallons per site (Resilient Chicago). A key goal of Chicago's green schoolyards is to bring benefits for the environment by:

- Reducing neighbourhood flooding by absorbing large amounts of rainwater
- Preventing combined sewer overflow to keeping the city's water resources clean
- Replacing asphalt with green space to reducing heat island effects and building resilience to climate change.

Figure 7: Greened schoolyard in Chicago (Greening Chicago schoolyards, 2019).

Green schoolyards in Chicago can be designed to mitigate climate change and positively influence the neighbourhood infrastructure (Space to grow, 2019). The approach to this challenge includes a focus on green infrastructure elements that can absorb large amounts of rainwater, thereby diverting the water from overtaxed sewage pipes and preventing it from flooding neighbourhood streets and basements. Chicago seeks to reduce flooding by incorporating landscape features that capture significant rainfall in the green schoolyard. These features include rain gardens, native plantings and gardens, permeable asphalt, permeable pavers, water storage, and permeable rubber play surfaces. These measures reduce flooding and mitigate runoff from polluting waterways (Resilient Chicago). The first 15 schoolyards combined can capture 2,511,569 gallons of water per rain event equivalent to 3.8 Olympic-sized swimming pools. The government and the partners have committed to building at least 34 schoolyards together in 2025, which are anticipated to capture over 5 million gallons of stormwater to keep that water out of the sewers during the heavy storms (Space to grow, 2019).

5.1 DONALD L. MORRILL MATH & SCIENCE SCHOOL, Chicago

5.1.1 SCHOOL CHALLENGES:

For decades, most Chicago schools did not have recess (Davis, 2015). District policy was only recently passed to reinstate recess in city schools. Over those years without recess, many Chicago schoolyards fell into disrepair, including Morrill school. In 2011, Chicago elementary schools (over 15 percent) had no playground equipment. Most Chicago schoolyards are covered in asphalt; many were converted to parking lots during the long recess drought and reduced the perceived costs of grass maintenance. 43% of Chicago Public Schools (CPS) students are overweight or obese (Davis, 2015). Morrill school has struggled to establish a trusting and collaborative relationship among its teachers. The performance in the category of trust went to 'weak'. Besides that, schools community performance score is "weak" in addressing parents feeling welcome at the school, parents sensing that school staff care about their students, and providing a sense of opportunity to participate in school decisions (Adnan, 2013).

5.1.2 GREEN SCHOOLYARD DESIGN:

Morrill Elementary is located in the Chicago Lawn neighbourhood in southwest Chicago. The School is redesigned to include a multipurpose turf field, play equipment for students of all ages, two half-court basketball courts, edible and learning gardens and disconnected downspouts that feed water into rain gardens with native plants. Besides that, the schoolyard includes a jogging track, vegetable gardens and rain gardens (Adnan, 2013). The renovation included tearing up large sections of crumbling asphalt and neglected playground equipment in a flood-prone neighbourhood and installing a multifaceted “green” schoolyard (Chicago elementary school to unveil new schoolyard, 2014). (see Figure 8)

Figure 8: Morrill school's after and before greening (HSC, 2015)

5.1.3 Green schoolyard role in the resilience of Morrill school:

5.1.3.1 Natural environment:

Green schoolyard in Morrill school is designed to enhance the resilience of the school toward flooding and stormwater (HSC, 2015; Resilient Chicago, n.d.). The schoolyards designed to capture significant amounts of rainfall (HSC, 2014; Thompson, 2017). The green space tackle flooding through green stormwater infrastructure (Donald I. Morrill math & science school, 2015). The brick ground around the schoolyard acts as a sponge since it is built with green infrastructure elements that help capture stormwater (Hutson, 2014). The school increased the green infrastructure to help about 4,500 plants put down new roots (HSC, 2014). Those plants used to inspire science lessons, art lessons and nutrition education (HSC, 2014). Some signage installed in the green schoolyard explains the stormwater management process and its value for the school (Resilient Chicago). According to table 2, the school contributed to reducing sediments, impervious cover, rate and volume of runoff water, and the average temperature in the school garden (Davis, 2015).

Table 2: Impact of greening Morrill schoolyard (Davis, 2015).

Project Name	Morrill Elementary School
Gallons of Stormwater Storage Added	6,660 (full to depth of 2 ft.)
Gallons of Rainwater Conserved Annually for Reuse	Unknown
Pounds of Sediment Removed, % Reduction	970 pds/acre/yr, 97% reduction
Area of Impervious Cover Removed (ft ²)	6,300
Area of Green Infrastructure Added (ft ²)	6,300
% Reduction in Rate of Runoff (ft ³ /sec/acre)	90% reduction in typical peak rate
% Reduction in Annual Volume of Runoff	90%
Average Temperature Reduction in Garden	13.5°F - 54.8°F
Number of K-12 Students Engaged	834
Number of Directly Involved Partners	Chicago Public Schools, City of Chicago Dept. of Water Mgmt., MWRD, Building School Gardens

5.1.3.2 Built environment:

The design transformed the schoolyard into vibrant outdoor spaces for the children (Chicago elementary school to unveil new schoolyard, 2014) for learning, play, engagement with nature and art (HSC, 2014). The grounds also feature areas for outdoor learning and exploration, including an outdoor classroom. Besides that, greening schoolyard ease playing soccer, flag football, basketball, cross country rather than the asphalt field (HSC, 2014) (Figure 9). The students who attend Morrill School will have plenty to do during recess now that it has a new soccer field and community garden (Hutson, 2014; WKKF, 2014).

Figure 9: Morrill school after the greening schoolyard (HSC, 2014)

5.1.3.3 Social Environment:

School leaders at Morrill noted the absence of criminal activity, graffiti and teenagers smoking and drinking on school grounds since the new schoolyard opened. In addition, the Consortium to Lower Obesity in Chicago Children (CLOCC) collected data to measure the impact of schoolyards on social cohesion. It is not statistically significant - due to sampling size- while it seemed that social cohesion had been increased (Davis, 2015), which increase the democratic social interactions between the children in the schoolyard and improved school environments (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Outdoor class in Morrill school (HSC, 2014)

5.1.3.4 Health & well-being:

Studies conducted in Morrill school show that equipped exterior play area enhances the learning environment resulting in improved learning and achievement and positive student development. Such play areas in the schools provide physical and mental challenges that translate to improved health and cognitive abilities in Morrill school (Adnan, 2013). The CLOCC collected data from schoolyards using accelerometers and observational tools showed a statistically significant increase in moderate to vigorous physical activity (Davis, 2015) among boys from 20.3 min to 49.6 min and trends among girls from 22.8 min to 28.1 min (Space to grow Chicago, n.d.). Activity increased in all grade levels studied due to greening schoolyards. The evaluation involved three grade levels (first, fourth and seventh grades), and students in all three grades showed increased activity. Statistically significant increases were evident among the 1st graders from 19.5 min to 27.8 min and 7th graders from 7.8 minutes to 27.9 minutes. Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity also increased among 4th graders from 31.7 min to 39.2 minutes (Space to grow Chicago, n.d.).

Figure 11: Garden pots in Morrill School (Space to grow, n.d.).

5.1.4 Green schoolyard role in the resilience Of Chicago lawn:

5.1.4.1 Natural environment:

The schoolyard has the added benefit of protecting the environment and reducing flooding in the Chicago Lawn neighbourhood (HSC, 2014). It was designed to include ground surfaces and landscape features that absorb large amounts of water, which will result in minor neighbourhood flooding (Hutson, 2014). Reducing runoff causes local flooding and flush street pollutants into the Chicago and Calumet rivers and Lake Michigan (HSC, 2014; Thompson, 2017). Morrill School saved 118,098 gallons (Space to Grow, sd); by lessening the load on the sewer system, they reduce flooding and improve area water quality (Grow, 2017). New green spaces produced cooling techniques because they encompass a significant range of methods, including replacing asphalt with grass in the schoolyard, the zoning of new community parks, and establishing fresh nature preserves. The transformation of schoolyards from blacktop to grass produced noticeable results. The transformation of the playing field and greenery at Morrill School cooled the area by approximately 0.9 °C by increasing NDVI by 0.15 (Mackey, 2012).

5.1.4.2 Built Environment:

The green schoolyard is opening to the neighbourhoods that lack park access. Thus, schools are opening green spaces to communities that require a place to gather. These green spaces are also designed for public use when school is not in session and expanding community outreach to new levels (Study International, 2019). These new play areas in Morrill school feed into an idea called “positive loitering,” which means filling the space with families and active kids to keep it safe for everyone (HSC, 2014). The surrounding communities use the schoolyard, it provides a place to gather, meet and enjoy, a place that enhances the community’s appearance (Adnan, 2013). Community members use the schoolyards for jogging and walking on the track, sit on benches to drink coffee, or take small children to play after school hours (Davis, 2015). Residents of the surrounding communities have expressed higher interest in attending schools with green schoolyards (Davis, 2015). The school is open to the public, there are no locks, and there are not many gates. Morrill school has built a green fence around the school. Therefore, these physical barriers promote a broader kind of openness (HSC, 2014). At the same time, the soccer players are coming back with bruises (Figure 12). It allows the inhabitants to come out at night to play (HSC, 2014). The schoolyard is not designed to be straightforward for pedestrians to cut through, keeping it from becoming an easy shortcut. Nevertheless, it is not closed off, either (HSC, 2014). Besides that, community-level data showed a rise in home prices in all neighbourhoods after opening the greened schoolyards (HSC, 2017).

Figure 12: Football field in Morrill school (HSC, 2014)

5.1.4.3 Social Environment:

When the schoolyard was unveiled, the changes were immense and immediately recognised by the surrounding community. The community felt that they had to drive across town to ride bikes to open the door and play. That affects the social and emotional being. It changes the climate and atmosphere of the neighbourhood (HSC, 2015). Since the schoolyard brings families together, the neighbours have taken ownership of the schoolyard it serves as a gathering place for years to come (HSC, 2015). The more people

Figure 13: Neighbourhood Gathering in Morrill School (HSC, 2014)

feel like the schoolyard is part of their space and their community, the more likely they are to respect it (HSC, 2014). Community in Chicago Lawn response toward the school was positive (Space to Grow, 2016). The community member survey data showed community felt positive about their community's social ties and cohesion and the number of safe playgrounds for kids to play and be active in their neighbourhood (Space to Grow, 2016). Space to Grow is working with Loyola University and the Nutrition Policy Institute at the University of California, and it reported that 50% of caregivers, 65% of teachers & 37% of community members thought that relations between the school & community changed following schoolyard transformation (Gerstein, 2017). Respondents reporting change cited better communication, more community involvement, greater community use of the playground, & increased neighbourhood pride as reasons for increased school-community relations (Figure 13). Based on the City of Chicago secondary data overall crime decreased, there was an uptick in violent crime at Morrill (Gerstein, 2017).

5.1.4.4 Health & wellbeing:

New play surfaces, soccer field, and basketball courts significantly impacted school athletics participation, and it brought the local community out to be more active (HSC, 2014). Changing schoolyards into green schoolyards centres of school enhances community life that supports active and healthy lifestyles, incorporates fresh produce and herbs from the garden into their daily cooking, and changed their lifestyle (HSC, 2015).

5.1.5 Conclusion of Morrill school:

The Morrill school, after greening, became a new access to community green space, new tool to address urban flooding and new school gardens and outdoor classrooms, and a new added public realm in the neighbourhood as in Table 3.

Table 3: Morrill's greening schoolyard Impacts

	Health	Social	Built	Natural
School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Improved academic achievement · Increase cognitive abilities · Boosting moderate to vigorous physical activity in boys · Boosting moderate to vigorous physical activity in girls · Increased physical activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Absence of criminal activity, graffiti, smoking and drinking · Increase social cohesion and interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Adding vibrant outdoor spaces with new functions; outdoor learning, play, engagement with nature and art · Green grass eases playing soccer, flag football, basketball 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Improving stormwater management and reducing flooding. · Increased the green infrastructure · Enhance science lessons, art lessons and nutrition education
Neighb.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Support active and healthy lifestyles · Increase usage of fresh produce and herbs from the garden into daily cooking. · Increase the neighbourhood physical activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reconnecting communities with local schools. · Enhance the social and emotional being. · Create school ownership · Positive response toward the school · More substantial relation between caregivers, teachers and community members · More community involvement, greater community use of the playground · Increased neighbourhood pride · Crime decreased, there was an uptick in violent crime 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Increase “positive loitering,” · School create a community place to gather · Host more activities · Higher interest in attending schools with green schoolyards. · Allows the inhabitants to come out at night and after school, hour to play. · Increase home prices in surroundings · Reduce physical barriers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Protecting the environment and reducing flooding · Reducing runoff that causes local flooding and flushes street pollutants · Lessening the load on the sewer system and also improving area water quality. · Reducing neighbourhood temperature.

CASE 2:

ROTTERDAM, THE NETHERLANDS HILDEGARDISSCHOOL

Student No.
400 - 500

Organization
BlauweGroen schoolplein

Location
Oude Noorden Neighbourhood

Construction Year
2011

CITY CHALLENGES:

Preparing for climate change:

The average temperature in the Netherlands has increased by 1.7 degrees since 1800 and the temperature increase in Rotterdam is even higher (Gemeente Rotterdam, n.d.). Because of dense buildings in the city, unlike green areas, it retains heat. The heat stress on sweltering days is hazardous for older and weaker residents. The increase in precipitation is another feature of climate change. It does not only related to raining more frequently, but significantly harder, where sometimes much precipitation falls in a short time. Sewers are overflow and the infrastructure cannot handle them. Adding to the problem is parking garages, roads, squares, and canals are flooding. Water storage is an essential solution to keep the city liveable (Gemeente Rotterdam, n.d.).

Noise pollution:

The port of Rotterdam and traffic contribute to a large extent to the noise pollution in the city. Noise is a growing health problem that mainly causes stress and fatigue due to disturbed sleep, especially for the people who live on or around main and access roads and busy streets. That is why the government wants to ensure a balance between quiet and the vibrant of the city (Gemeente Rotterdam, n.d.).

GREEN SCHOOLYARDS ROLE IN RESILIENT ROTTERDAM:

The adaptive capacity in Rotterdam has been much focused on improving overall green infrastructure and implementing new ways for integrated planning to improve the quality of life (Tillie, 2016). One of the ways in increasing green spaces is the creation of more green schoolyards. Twelve schoolyards were turned into green. Rotterdam invests in twenty hectares of extra greenery in the city - this is stated in the Rotterdam action plan goes green (Tillie, 2016). Consequently, in the inner city, the percentage of inhabitants that have green and water within 300 m has increased by 8% since 2001 (Tillie, 2016). Rotterdam's Green Blue Schoolyards programme tackle child-friendliness and climate resilience with more nature in schoolyards. The programme is launched to supports schools to transform their outdoor spaces into natural play areas for outdoor educational projects and community use. These schoolyards are known to provide compound benefits to city authorities and residents: lower stress levels, better mental health, active and healthier lifestyles, better stormwater management, increased real estate values and reduced heat island effects (Green Blue Schoolyards, 2021).

5.2 HILDEGARDISSCHOOL SCHOOL, Rotterdam

5.2.1 SCHOOL CHALLENGES:

5.2.1.1 Lack of play equipment:

The original schoolyards of the Hildegardisschool is a predominantly grey tiled square with some playground equipment. Furthermore, the school lacks places where different activities could occur, such as quiet place or opportunities to retreat with a small group or alone. The schoolyard and its layout are provided little shelter from the rain in the winter since there is no shelter from certain weather conditions or the gaze of others (de Vries et al., 2013).

5.2.1.2 Lack of green:

Only some strips of shrubbery separate the schoolyard from the rest of the school, and the schoolyard itself has a few solitary trees. Even though these green structures enhance the schoolyard's appearance, they cannot guarantee a 'green', comfortable environment. It is almost impossible to discover any greenery near the school. Trees and shrubs considered green is not meant to be played in or around, so they can only be viewed as only viewing-green (de Vries et al., 2013).

5.2.1.3 Insecure and unsafe location:

The schoolyard is located in the middle of a residential area with traffic on the roads, which usually cause a lot of crowds and traffic noise. Moreover, the play equipment is located at the edge of the playground, which means danger and risks the children safety. Besides that, the playground equipment is old; therefore, it could create a danger to the children who play with it (de Vries et al., 2013).

5.2.2 Green schoolyard design:

Half the square is public and can be used by residents even outside school hours. A grass, a swamp pond, and a discovery garden have been implemented in new design, and on the side of the school, they have built a children's vegetable garden (Arntz, 2011). The schoolyard is divided into six different zones: educational herb and flower garden, pavement tile square, vegetable garden, two playing fields and a football cage (Figure 14). The two playing fields, which cover a large part of the total schoolyard, are about 40 cm raised from street level and have a concrete block edge. The different zones of the schoolyard each have an explicit function of their own and are distinguishable. These different zones are connected with the same tiles, creating a clear structure. (de Vries et al., 2013).

Figure 14: Hildergradisschool after greening (Arntz, 2011)

5.2.3 Green schoolyard role in the resilience of Hildergradisschool:

5.2.3.4 Natural Environment:

A study was done by de Vries et al. (2013) on four different greened schoolyards in Rotterdam, including Hildergradisschool. They measured the impacts at two different time intervals and held interviews with teachers from grade 3, 4 and 5. The distinct impacts aspect of greening was to focus on how children connect with nature and their attitude towards it. Among the underlying assumptions was that redesigning schoolyards in a greener way positively influence the students' attitude and lead to improved bonding. However, no significant before/after differences have been found for this effect. Children's nature attitude was significantly influenced by the natural attitude of the teaching team and the pedagogical climate in particular (Breman, 2013). The students ought to treat nature more respectfully. The children were looking for animals: snails, spiders everywhere at the school. Nature integrated with them more (de Vries et al., 2013). In grade 3, the teacher indicated that her students were accustomed to

being stewards of the school's natural resources than they were previously. In particular, the observation that the students leave the plants in the ground demonstrates they are also careful not to stand on the plants or harm them (de Vries et al., 2013). Students in fourth grade also indicated that they liked to maintain the new schoolyard and keep it beautiful (de Vries et al., 2013). While the fifth-grade students were particularly interested in exploring the surrounding school gardens for the first time after the green schoolyard had just been laid out

Students searched and found animals, which were then displayed with pride in the presence of their teacher. They have also become more aware of the different plants that grow and thrive in the student gardens. The educational flower and herb garden has also attracted birds to use it in literary form (de Vries et al., 2013). The pond is the only place in the school garden where group 3 students explore. It enthuses them greatly to see all kinds of aquatic creatures swimming in the water. Nonetheless, this teacher indicates that she sometimes considers this exploratory behaviour dangerous. Since students must climb on the stones around the pond to see what lives in the water, they increase their chances of falling into the water (Arntz, 2011; de Vries et al., 2013).

5.2.3.3 Built Environment:

The teachers of grades 3 and 4 indicate that the pupils now have several play opportunities and play facilities than before. The green schoolyard was much more challenging due to the playground equipment and the shape of the schoolyard (de Vries et al., 2013). The grass also offered the pupils the space to lie down in a chill area, as in Figure 15 (de Vries et al., 2013). The new schoolyard provides more variation in playgrounds and plays facilities. The teachers supposed that more students could perform various activities in the schoolyard during the breaks and after-school (de Vries et al., 2013).

Figure 15: Hildegardisschool design (Arntz, 2011)

The teacher of group 5 noticed that after school, more students are using the schoolyard than before. She indicated that previously the old schoolyard was also used, but is used more often and more intensively after the greening (de Vries et al., 2013). Although the number of pupils playing in the square has not changed much, it seems less crowded, probably because pupils can now spread out better over the different fields within the schoolyard. A plausible explanation for this is that the leeway in the schoolyard has increased in two means; more variety in play possibilities and larger square meters (de Vries et al., 2013). For the teachers of grades 3 and 4, the green schoolyard is more educational, in which lessons can be held (de Vries et al., 2013). The students are observing things for themselves in the outdoor lessons that made the schoolyard more educational and a place to play and discover (Arntz, 2011).

The different sizes of the zones contribute to the social variation on the schoolyard, which means that there are places for smaller groups and places for larger groups and interesting places for older children and places that are especially interesting for younger children. The

restructuring of the schoolyard, with the different zones, has resulted in smaller-scale places. In the vegetable garden, when the beech hedge is at height, the pupils are sheltered from severe weather conditions and the sights of the passers-by. Therefore, create an intimate, atmospheric place where students can retreat alone or with a small group from the rest of the children (de Vries et al., 2013).

5.2.3.2 Social Environment:

The assessment has been done on three school grades (grade 3, grade 4 and grade 5) in the primary school. The teacher of grade 4 did not indicate changes regarding quarrelling between the students, while the teacher of grade 5 does state that there is less quarrelling between the students after redesigning the schoolyard. The third-grade teacher thinks that there may be less fighting than before, mainly because there is more variation in playing opportunities (de Vries et al., 2013). This study showed a connection between the green redevelopment of the schoolyard and improved social climate. Different children can undertake more different activities, which leads to a decrease in the number of disturbances between children (Breman, 2013). Since the green schoolyard is found to be more attractive. With an improved social environment, children have more respect for each other and less fighting and bullying (de Vries et al., 2013). The exact causes of these changes in play behaviour were complicated for the teachers to indicate, but a combination of the greenery with the new playground equipment seems to be the most feasible (de Vries et al., 2013). Previously the girls hardly had any space on the old schoolyard. It was dominated by boys playing football. After the redesigning, the girls started to find their place (de Vries et al., 2013). The child's assessment showed that the social climate in the schoolyard was positively related to well-being in general and specific aspects of self-image.

5.2.3.1 Health & wellbeing:

There were impacts of greening schoolyards on the children's health. For example, the child's ability to concentrate after the morning break was positive, according to the assessment of the schoolyard. Besides that, they reported a positive relationship between a green redesign and the higher well-being of the children as the overall mental health and physical well-being of the children has increased (Breman, 2013). The improvements appeared in the ability of the child to concentrate, child mood after the morning break, child well-being and self-image (de Vries et al., 2013). The mental health improvement after the new green schoolyard has been evident in the students creative playing, as they have developed many more new games and ideas. (Figure 16) (de Vries et al., 2013).

Figure 16: children playing with nature (Arntz, 2011)

5.2.4 Green schoolyard role in the resilience of Oude Noorden:

5.2.4.4 Natural Environment:

Parents are becoming increasingly aware of the function of the green environment. The parents from the neighbourhood are helping the gardener with the maintenance. The garden committee becomes popular because many parents like to do something to make the neighbourhood greener. Moreover, the school enhanced the biodiversity in the neighbourhood by looking at the adopted nature. The variation in trees, shrubs and herbs (Healthy city, sd). There are trees and shrubs, shell paths, steppingstones and tree trunks to climb (de Vries et al., 2013). However, one of the negatives of opening it to the public is that the neighbourhood children pollute the pond or use it as a waste bin, which drove everything into it.

5.2.4.3 Built Environment:

Setting up the green schoolyard within public or non-public makes a big difference. On a non-public schoolyard, the focus has been on learning with fun, while at a public square, it is about entertaining all local target groups. Furthermore, after-school care can also use the schoolyard. Thus, more children may benefit from the schoolyard because it is also used outside school hours. Especially the kids are entering the green schoolyard to play after school. For the neighbourhoods there become varied public play and sports areas with more opportunities for meeting. The schoolyard refers to a friendly and secure environment in the school as a priority. Young inhabitants of the neighbourhood are likely to come across the greened schoolyard, as there are almost no green spaces or lakes nearby (de Vries et al., 2013).

5.2.4.2 Social Environment:

The schoolyard is half public property and can be used by the local community. It has become a popular site and is used by more local citizens. Additionally, the youths loitering had disappeared from the playing fields (de Vries et al., 2013). Regardless of origin or faith, community members thrive best in an environment where they feel safe, valued, and respected. Furthermore, involve other residents in the maintenance of the green playground (Arntz, 2011). Aside from that, the landscaped greenery impacts the atmosphere between students and people from the neighbourhood. Therefore, the people learned to become slightly kinder, a little gentler, and less prone to becoming angry (de Vries et al., 2013).

5.2.4.1 Health and wellbeing:

The green schoolyards are committed to a healthy school environment with a smoke-free zone. Moreover, residents and caregivers can find opportunities close to their homes for high-quality sports facilities, such as gymnasiums and other sports, to play and exercise, which leads to an increase in the physical activity of the neighbours.

5.2.5 Conclusion of Hildegardisschool :

The school has tackled neighbourhood challenges even though it is semi-public (see Table 4) by raising awareness between the parents and the community. Moreover, it enhances biodiversity, creates a social atmosphere. At the school scale, the green schoolyard created various play opportunities for different groups. Besides, the green led to improved bonding with nature and created a social climate in the school.

Table 4: Hildegardisschool greening schoolyard Impacts

	Health	Social	Built	Natural
School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Indirect impact on the children's health. · Enhance child's ability to concentrate · Increased overall mental health and physical well-being · Improvements in child mood after the morning break, child well-being and self-image 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Positive social climate in the school. · Gender equality in playing opportunity · Different outcomes in each grade concerning quarrelling and fighting between the students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Several play opportunities and play facilities · Offered the pupils the space to lie down · Usage during the breaks and after-school · More students are using the schoolyard than before. · Less crowded because pupils spread out over the different fields. · Become more educational 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Positively influence the students' attitude and lead to improved bonding with nature. · Children's nature attitude is influenced by the natural attitude of the pedagogical climate. · The students treat nature more respectfully. · Students have become more aware of the different plants · The educational flower used in literary form. · The pond used by students to explore. · Exploratory behaviour was dangerous
Neighb.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Increased the smoke-free area · Offer opportunities for the neighbours to a high quality sport facilities. · Increase the residents physical activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · It used more by Local residents · The youths loitering have disappeared · Involve residents in the maintenance of the green playground. · Enhance the atmosphere between students and community · Reduce the behaviour of anger · It creates safe, valued, and respected environment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · More children from after-school care use it · On a non-public section, the focus on learning with fun · On a public section, the focus on entertaining locals. · Maintaining a safe school climate, friendly and secure environment. · Add a new public space to the neighbourhood with varied public areas to play and more places to meet. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Parents are becoming increasingly aware of the function of the green environment. · The garden committee becomes popular. · The school enhances the neighbourhood biodiversity · One of the negatives is that the neighbourhood children are polluting the pond

CASE 3:

Amsterdam, The Netherlands
S.B.O HET UNIVERSUM SCHOOL

Student No.
150

Organization
Amsterdamse Impulse schoolplein

Location
Amsterdam Noord

Construction Year
2018

CITY CHALLENGES:

Water-related hazards are taken into consideration by the city of Amsterdam. The city has also faced rapid densification of the city centre. Improving the quality of life and the accessibility of green spaces are among the main priorities. 'Structural Vision: Amsterdam 2040' is the 2010 city-region plan that set the investment and project ambitions for 2010-2040. The strategy seeks to fulfil a creative and varied city vision, integrated high-quality urban planning, and investment in recreational green spaces. Water-related hazards, such as storm surges and floods, are managed at all levels (Wijten, 2015). The city needs multifunctional green space, which provides multiple benefits. In recent years, much of this valuable green space has been added to the city's streets. These green spaces include pocket parks, **green schoolyards**, nature play parks, green strips along the water, green play streets, sidewalk gardens, and green roofs (van der Veur, 2017).

GREEN SCHOOLYARDS ROLE IN RESILIENT AMSTERDAM:

According to Amsterdam city report, published in 2017 about their vision to build a green resilience city, they mentioned that "Schoolyards designed as an area to play and learn, such as an outdoor classroom with animals, plants and trees". This type of space benefits the school children, teachers, and the local neighbourhood, especially as more and more schoolyards are made (Semi-)Public and more accessible. Amsterdam is investing in redesign schoolyard to increase green, climate-proof places and encourage children to play, learn and explore (van der Veur, 2017). Greening schoolyard participated in enhancing greenery in the city by increasing the number of trees. Besides, it contributes to strengthening the community, enhancing the biodiversity, climate resilience and health of the student and the well being as in Figure 17.

benefits

intervention	community	biodiversity	recreation and aesthetics	climate resilience	education and development	health
pocket park, neighbourhood park	•	•	•	•		•
green play area, nature play park	•	•	•	•	•	•
green schoolyard	•	•		•	•	•
trees		•	•	•		
green strip	•	•	•	•	•	•
green play street	•	•	•	•	•	•
sidewalk garden	•	•	•	•		
semi-public or private garden	•	•	•	•		•
green roof	•	•	•	•		•

Figure 17: Green city's intervention benefits (van der Veur, 2017)

AIS ambition:

In a report published by Amsterdamse Impulse schoolpleinen in 2021, 70 schoolyards were greened and challengingly decorated from 2016 to 2018. From 2019 to 2024, AIS wants to redesign a further 60 schoolyards, as in Figure 18. In the context of equality of opportunity, AIS prioritises schools and pupils in development neighbourhoods who need this impulse most. The schoolyards get more trees and plants and are arranged to be more suitable for exercise, nature education and drainage of rainwater (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2021).

Figure 18: Overview map of AIS (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2021)

The exact impacts of greening schoolyard back to the AIS report in 2021 (Figure 19) the natural and safe playground increased by 138.659m² in January 2021. The public and semi-public playgrounds become 41.088m². The greened schoolyard participated in the greenery in the city by 33.324m². The city of Amsterdam decreased the asphalt and pavement by around 33.437m² from the city. Moreover, increase the smoking-free place to be 86, while in 2018, it was 70 places. (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2021).

Figure 19: Impacts of green schoolyard in AIS (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2021)

5.3 HET UNIVERSUM SCHOOL

5.3.1 SCHOOL CHALLENGES:

5.3.1.1 Lack of playgrounds:

S.B.O. Het Universum school is located directly on the Baanackerspark in Amsterdam Noord. Het Universum is primary special-needs education. The outdoor space was bare: concrete tiles, steel fencing, some square slicers as in Figure 20. The kind of plays that were exist focused on games that require a lot of concentration and social abilities. The schoolyard consists of 3 parts: superstructure square, middle square, substructure square; all squares have a boring and non-child-friendly look (Altes, 2017).

Figure 20: Het Universum school before greening (Google map,2017)

5.3.1.2 Lack of green:

There is only one tree in the middle square. Otherwise, there is no greenery in the schoolyard. However, the teachers realised that their pupils show different behaviours in nature. Moreover, lack of greening lead to drainage problems in the school on severe rainy days (Altes, 2017).

5.3.1.3 Special need student:

Students of S.B.O Universum have learning or behavioural difficulties. In addition to that, the students have less ability to focus, pay attention, listen, or put effort into schoolwork. The students suffer from fidgetiness, restlessness, less in concentration or disrupt the class. They might also have learning disabilities that cause them to have problems in school (Altes, 2017).

5.3.2 GREEN SCHOOLYARD DESIGN

In principle, the entire schoolyard is re-tiled, including concrete slab, displacement of chutes. The removed paving structure in the schoolyard was 593m² (Altes, 2017). The former football field on the concrete slab is re-paved so that there is a better slope to allow the drainage to go directly towards the green. It has been designed to add football field lines of 2 pitches instead of 1 large field to reactivate spots all over the schoolyard, such as swing hammock, open fields for jumping rope, running stilts, climbing, green boxes filled with green and herbs (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Het Universum Green schoolyard

5.3.3 Green schoolyards role in resilient Universum school:

5.3.3.1 Natural environment:

According to Jurre, a concierge at SBO Universum, **“Nature in the schoolyard raised the children’s awareness toward the small living critters likes bees, insects, worms, lizards, birds. Besides that, it encourages the student to maintain the green, respect, and appreciate nature and learn to be cautious about nature when necessary”**. The teacher realised that integrating outdoor learning programs related to enhancing climate change increases awareness about climate change. The students experience the rewards of fresh vegetables and understand the natural growth of plants and the impact that drought, rain and other features of the nature. The schoolyard includes boxes for gardening, making student participants express more positive insights on nature and environmental issues. Besides, adding the green infrastructure in the school resulted in much less pressure on chutes and the school’s sewer system. Moreover, greening the schoolyard enrich the biodiversity in the school, including:

- 1- Large shrubs smell, bloom in various seasons, such as red and yellow dogwood.
- 2- Educational & edible green, such as raspberry, blueberries, two fruit trees (apple/pear).
- 3- Strain & discover green around play equipment, strong shrubs, hazel, cat willow,
- 4- Herb vegetable: thyme, lemon balm, rosemary, lemon zest, chocolate mint and mint.
- 5- Feel and scent planter, several vigorous plants

5.3.3.2 Built Environment:

The new schoolyard provides new and variant places to play for the different students needs at different time of the day (Altes, 2017). First, it included new prolific play equipment that offers variety of play options like horizontal climbing, as in Figure 22. Secondly, the schoolyard pavement has been decorated with a plaque for free play and diverse movement play. Thirdly, the open fields for various play like stilts, jumping rope, roller skates (Altes, 2017). Fourth, fields for sport with multifunctional lines for different sports

Figure 22: Challenging play

such as volleyball poles and table tennis against sports field. It also provides different zones for different uses and activities; an extra piece of the schoolyard becomes a green chill and rest zone, surrounded by flowering shrubs. It creates a zen place to retreat, a quiet place overlooking the pond. Another activity is the outdoor class and reading place in green with the view of the park outside the school. The new re-designed schoolyard has built green fencing to reduce the barrier between the school and the outdoor park. Students in Het Universum characterised the schoolyard as peace and calm place since they experienced naturalised habitat and relaxation in the gardens.

5.3.3.3 Social Environment:

Based on the interview with Jurre, **“The children become less aggressive toward each other, their social skills have been improved by finding new ways to play and cooperate”**. According to him the children with learning disabilities, the greened schoolyard involvement has been shown to enhance nonverbal communication skills and participation in their cooperative tasks. Students in Het Universum

school showed an improvement in cooperation to achieve group goals in the green space outside the classrooms. Lower verbal and physical conflict rates immediately post-greening followed by significantly lower antisocial interactions. Nature encouraged the teamwork, and increased interaction between children in the school.

5.3.3.4 Health and well being:

The teacher did not realize a change in the children's academic achievement; since they already have learning difficulties. However, Mona and Jurre realized a significant change in children's mental health well-being that reduced aggression, self-harm, soiling, smearing, and shouting. They become calmer, less stressed and more willing to play outside.

5.3.4 Green schoolyards role in resilient Amsterdam Noord school:

Het Universum school is not noticeable within the fences. The school is mainly for special education. Thus, it is not open to the public after school hours, and it has been fenced off from the neighbourhood. In addition to that, the school is lower than the road level as in Figure 23; it is hidden from eyesight. Therefore based on the interview with Mona, Jurre, and the observational investigation, the greened schoolyard has minor influences on the surrounding, and change has not even realized after greening for the neighbours or the teachers.

Figure 23: Het Universum school from the road (Google map, 2021)

Natural environment:

However, the greening interventions in Het Universum, schoolyard, did have some minor influences on the neighbourhood natural environment. By removing 593m² of paved surfaces, the pressure on the neighbourhood sewer system in the severe raining days is decreased. Moreover, the various plants in the green schoolyard incorporate and enhance the biodiversity of the neighbourhood. Based on the literature review, the amount of greenery added to the school could reduce the heat stress in the neighbourhood, reduce the heat temperature, and reduce the air pollutions and noise from the main road.

5.3.5 Conclusion of Het Universum school:

The main impacts of the green schoolyard in Het Universum school were on the school's resilience, as shown in Table 5. On the other hand, the schoolyard was not open to the public. Therefore, the influences on the neighbourhood resilience were only on the natural environment resilience, but the other factors were not recognizable for the teachers or the neighbours, since it requires the school to be open to public.

Table 5: Conclusion of Het Universum school

	Health	Social	Built	Natural
School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The teacher did not realize a change in the children's academic achievement · A significant change in children's mental health well-being · The student become calmer, less stressed and more willing to play outside. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The children become less aggressive · Social skills have been improved by finding new ways to play and cooperate. · Encourage teamwork · Increased interaction between children, teachers · Enhance nonverbal communication skills, attitudes toward order · Lower verbal and physical conflict rates post-greening. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Provides a new place to play for the student for free play and diverse movement play. · Provides zones for different uses and activities · Provides a green chill and rest zone. · Reduce the barrier by making green fence · The school added an observation area. · The schoolyard characterised as peace and calmed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Raised the children's awareness toward the small living critters · Respect nature · Increasing awareness about greening and climate change. · The children experience the rewards of fresh produce · More positive outlooks on nature, gardening · Lower the pressure on chutes and the sewer system of the school. · Enhance biodiversity in the school
Neigh				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Decrease the pressure on sewer system in the severe raining days · Enhance the biodiversity of the neighbourhood. · Reduce the heat stress , · Reduce the air pollutions and noise from the street.

5.4 CONCLUSION OF THE EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

Opening or closing the greened schoolyard from the public does not affect the school resilience. As discussed above in all three case studies, the greened schoolyard could cope and tackle the school challenges and improve the school and the student resilience. On the other hand, the neighbourhood resilience has been affected by opening the greened schoolyard to public use. In the first two cases in Morrill school and Hildegardisschool, the greened schoolyard has been able to contribute to the neighbourhood and even the city resilience in a multisystem approach. While in Amsterdam, the green schoolyard was not open to the public after school-hour or contributed to the neighbourhood's green infrastructure. Therefore, Het Universum green schoolyard does not affect the community or the neighbourhood resilience in social, built or health as long as it is isolated from the neighbourhood by fences and not open for public use.

6 RESEARCH CONCLUSION

“Public schoolyard can be so much more” (Loder, 2018). This quote becomes evident throughout the research paper and answers the main research question, “How can socio-ecological resilience model used to analyse the impact of greening schoolyards on school and neighbourhood?” The research paper aimed to broaden the conversation on the potential for green schoolyards to contribute to socio-ecological resilience in the face of an unpredictable future challenged by climate variability, and availability and equitable distribution of resources. Based on qualitative data analysis in three frameworks theoretical, analytical and application, this thesis has shown that green schoolyard has a dual role; it could be place-based education and community hub. It has many benefits for multiple stakeholders starts from students, families, caregivers and communities.

Green schoolyards play a small but essential role The findings imply that green schoolyards are an essential tool in supporting socio-ecological resilience in school and neighbourhood. Because it enables resource managers to identify opportunities to reduce risk through natural (nature) and physical (schoolyard design) interventions. The resilience created by the green schoolyard relates to competence in developmental tasks and risks, to the positive development of the children and community’s well-being, social, urban and natural environment. The innovative use of the greening schoolyards with natural features is intended to enhance the space’s ecological, vibrancy, social and pedagogical value. In the end, the greened schoolyard can impact multiple geographic and social scales from entire cities to individuals with multisystem approaches and disciplines in addressing various issues and disasters.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on this conclusion, firstly, within the context of current estimates that extreme weather conditions and the recent Covid-19, creating more green infrastructure in schoolyards more viable options to cope with climate change and corona pandemic. Therefore, an important recommendation is to involve greening multiple schoolyards in the neighbourhood and cities actively. Moreover, school lessons need to be combined with the physical design by making them part of the pedagogical climate in the school.

Secondly, this research paper recommends that the city that develops resilience plans should add a strategy for greening schoolyards in each neighbourhood and adopt them on the long-term approach. Local-scale greening planning such a green schoolyard must occur within a city-level framework and develop it through a multisystem process to ensure that local projects synergistically contribute to an integrated city-scale system and significantly impact the smallest scale.

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8 APPENDIX

8.1 FIRST INTERVIEW SETTING

8.1.1 Location

The interview was at the schoolyard of S.B.O Het Universum

8.1.2 Interviewee

Jurre Nopper is a Congerice in S.B.O school before greening the schoolyard

8.1.3 Duration of the Interview

The interview was 20 minutes

8.1.4 Question that has been asked

- 1- Why has the school decided to green the schoolyards? What were the main challenges?
- 2- What was the change that surprised you the most?
- 3- What is the significant change you have realized?
- 4- Does the schoolyard change the student vision/behaviour toward nature?
- 5- How did the level of the activity change after greening?
 - Concentration
 - Aggression behaviour
 - Academic achievement
 - Stress
 - Socio-wellbeing
 - Gender equality
- 6- How playing behaviour change?
- 7- What did the new green schoolyard offer the children
 - Place to relax
 - Place to play
 - Place to learn
- 8- Is it open to the public after school hour? Why?
- 9- Do you think the neighbourhood is aware of greening? Or by the new children behaviour?

8.1 SECOND INTERVIEW SETTING

8.1.1 Location

The interview was via zoom Meeting

8.1.2 Interviewee

Mona Fathalla is a mother for a girl student in the school since 2017, she also live in the neighbourhood of Buikslotermeer within 250 meter from the school.

8.1.3 Duration of the Interview

The interview was 10 minutes

8.1.4 Question that has been asked

- 1- Did you realized that the school has been greened?
- 2- What was the change that surprised you the most?
- 3- What is the significant change you have realized?
- 4- Does the schoolyard change the student vision/behaviour toward nature?
- 5- How did the level of the activity change after greening?
 - Aggression behaviour
 - Stress
- 6- How playing behaviour change?
- 7- Do you think the neighbourhood is aware of greening?

